

Multifunctional implantable hydrogels: Smart platforms at the forefront of biomedical innovation

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Abstract

Hydrogels are a transformative class of biomaterials with high water content, intrinsic biocompatibility, and tunable mechanical, chemical, and biological properties. These three-dimensional polymeric networks closely mimic the extracellular matrix, making them ideal for implantable biomedical applications. This review provides a comprehensive overview of implantable hydrogel technologies, focusing on critical physicochemical and biological features that determine clinical performance. Recent advances in additive manufacturing fabrication techniques, including 3D and 4D printing, are explored alongside innovations in hydrogel ink formulations designed to enhance mechanical robustness, shape fidelity, and biological functionality. Special attention is given to the infection-preventive roles of hydrogels, both as implant coatings and injectable platforms. Surface modification strategies—covalent and non-covalent—are discussed in the context of improving biocompatibility and preventing microbial colonization. Injectable hydrogels are further examined for their antimicrobial efficacy, particularly within stimuli-responsive drug delivery systems and multifunctional platforms, with an emphasis on translational challenges from in vitro studies to clinical application. The regenerative potential of hydrogels is also highlighted, especially in bone tissue engineering, focusing on osteoconductivity, osteoinductivity, vascularization, and regulatory considerations. Additionally, implantable hydrogel-based patches for real-time health monitoring are evaluated, including emerging biosensing technologies and their integration into clinical practice. Despite significant progress, challenges remain in large-scale manufacturing, long-term stability, and regulatory approval. Future perspectives emphasize the development of smart, multifunctional hydrogels with integrated biosensing and responsive therapeutic delivery, highlighting their potential to advance personalized medicine and improve patient outcomes.

Keywords. Additive manufacturing, hydrogel ink formulation, injectable biomaterials, antimicrobial hydrogels, bone tissue engineering, real-time health monitoring, personalized medicine

1. INTRODUCTION

Hydrogels, defined as 3D crosslinked polymeric networks, exhibit biocompatibility, high water absorption capacity, and the ability to recapitulate the extracellular matrix (ECM) while encapsulating and delivering cells and therapeutics [1, 2]. These characteristics have positioned hydrogels as a pivotal platform in biomedical science and clinical applications. Continued advances in materials science, fabrication technologies, and biological understanding have notably transformed conventional hydrogels—once limited by poor controllability and insufficient smart responsiveness—into sophisticated, multifunctional biomaterials with adaptive properties, customizable architectures, and expanding functional capabilities. As next-generation biomaterials, hydrogels are demonstrating significant clinical relevance across a broad range of controlled drug delivery, as well as therapeutic, regenerative and diagnostic applications [3-6].

Among the various hydrogel platforms, implantable hydrogels (IHGs) designed for surgical or minimally invasive placement into the body, have attracted considerable interest for their potential application as localized therapeutic platforms [7], regenerative scaffolds [8], wearable health monitoring devices [4], and human-machine bio-interfaces [1, 9, 10]. IHGs can be classified based on their physical state and mode of administration into solid preformed matrices [11] and injectable, in situ-forming liquid systems [12]. Preformed IHGs are synthesized and crosslinked *ex vivo*, allowing immediate function upon implantation [13, 14]. They offer high shape fidelity, mechanical stability, and structural precision, making them suitable for bone and cartilage regeneration [6, 15], wound healing [16], ocular implants [17] and sustained drug delivery systems [11]. However, implantation often requires invasive procedures, especially for non-biodegradable systems, posing risks in sensitive areas such as the eye [18]. Their fixed geometry also limits adaptability to irregular defects, reducing utility in complex tissue environments [19]. On the other hand, injectable in situ-forming HGs are delivered as liquid precursors that gel under physiological conditions, forming ECM-like 3D networks [20]. Gelation can be triggered by temperature, pH, enzymes, light, or ionic interactions, and is tailored to specific applications [21]. Some injectable hydrogels are shear-thinning preformed types that regain their structure after injection [22]. Injectable HGs allow minimally invasive delivery conforming to complex anatomies, enhancing tissue integration, and their stimuli-responsive nature supports controlled release of drugs, biotherapeutics, cells, and nanoparticles [23-26]. However, they generally have lower mechanical strength post-gelation compared to their preformed counterparts and face challenges in gelation consistency, reproducibility, and scalable manufacturing [27].

Further classification of IHGs by polymer source, crosslinking method, stimuli responsiveness, structure, and degradability enables precise tailoring for biomedical applications. Hydrogels are commonly divided into natural (e.g., collagen, alginate, gelatin, chitosan) and synthetic (e.g., polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid (PLGA) types) [28]. Natural polymers offer biocompatibility and bioactivity but often lack mechanical robustness [29]. While synthetic polymers provide mechanical tunability and reproducibility, though they may require

functionalization and/or hybridization with natural polymers to enhance bioactivity [30]. Based on crosslinking, IHGs are categorized as chemically (covalently) or physically (reversibly) crosslinked. Chemically crosslinked hydrogels using crosslinking agents like genipin and glutaraldehyde, or photoinitiators to promote covalent bonding through processes like photopolymerization or enzymatic coupling, have demonstrated to offer high mechanical stability for long-term implantation [31]. In contrast, physically-crosslinked hydrogels rely on reversible, non-covalent interactions, such as electrostatic interactions, hydrogen bonding, or hydrophobic associations [32]. These hydrogels are often stimuli-responsive, enabling dynamic behaviours as a response to stimuli like changes in pH, temperature, or enzymatic-activity. Accordingly, IHGs may be further subclassified into responsive (smart) and non-responsive systems based on their environmental adaptability. Structurally, IHGs include single networks, interpenetrating polymer networks (IPNs), and double-network systems, which enhance mechanical performance [33, 34]. In terms of size, IHGs range from bulk hydrogels to microgels (10–1000 μm) and nanogels (<1000 nm), with smaller forms favoured for injectability and targeted delivery [35]. Lastly, degradable IHGs—via hydrolysis or enzymatic action—are suited for transient therapies, while non-degradable variants support long-term structural roles.

Multifunctional IHGs have emerged as the next-generation systems representing a transformative class of biomaterials designed to integrate multiple capabilities, such as stimuli-responsiveness, controlled therapeutic delivery, and real-time monitoring, within a single platform. This multifunctionality significantly enhances therapeutic efficacy and expands their potential across diverse clinical settings [36, 37]. Thus, to meet the complex demands of biomedical applications, multifunctional IHGs are engineered with precisely tailored material properties [38]. A critical attribute is mechanical tunability, which ensures that the hydrogel's stiffness, elasticity, and toughness align with the mechanical characteristics of target tissues [38]. This tunability is achieved by varying the polymer type/concentration [39], crosslinking density/method [40] as well as the addition of fillers such as nanoparticles [41], nanocrystals [42] and nanofibers [43]. Beyond mechanical adaptation, many IHGs are designed to possess self-healing and stretchable properties, introduced through dynamic bonding strategies, enabling the hydrogel to withstand physiological movements and recover from damage, a property of importance for strain/pressure wearable devices [44] and anti-freezing hydrogels [45, 46]. Stimuli-responsiveness is another hallmark of advanced IHGs. Sensitivity to temperature, pH or redox conditions [47, 48] enables on-demand functionalities for applications such as controlled drug release [49], wound healing [50], and endodontics [51]. In parallel, incorporating electrically conductive components, such as polypyrrole or graphene, allows the hydrogels to interface with various tissues for wearable sensing [52] and promote the healing of chronic wounds [52, 53]. Equally important, biocompatibility is ensured by using natural polymers, often combined with bioactive cues for therapeutic and tissue regeneration applications [54]. For temporary implants, controlled degradability is achieved using biodegradable polymers, eliminating the need for surgical removal [55, 56]. Finally, strong tissue adhesion, often inspired by mussel-inspired catechol chemistries,

has been reported to facilitate intimate integration with host tissues, further improving clinical performance [57].

Altogether, these properties position multifunctional IHGs as versatile platforms for diverse applications. For example, in therapeutic delivery, their stimuli-responsiveness and degradability can enable localized, controlled release of drugs or bioactive compounds, enhancing treatment efficacy while minimizing systemic adverse effects. This is particularly of benefit in cancer therapy [58, 59], chronic inflammation [60], and infection control [61]. As tissue-supporting scaffolds, their mechanical tunability, biocompatibility, and bioactivity promote cell adhesion and regeneration, supporting repair in bone and cartilage [6], spinal cord [56], and cardiac tissues [62]. In bioelectronics, their conductivity and compliance with soft tissues enable real-time sensing and stimulation, advancing applications such as implantable biosensors [63], electroactive wound dressings [53], and neural interfaces [64, 65].

To frame the growing importance of IHG technologies within the broader scientific landscape, a targeted bibliometric survey was performed using the Web of Science Core Collection (June 12, 2025), covering publications from 2018 to 2025. The search, restricted to original research articles and reviews, employed the terms “implantable” and “hydrogels” in titles, abstracts, or keywords to capture studies directly relevant to the field. While not the primary aim of this work, this analysis provides an evidence-based snapshot of recent research dynamics, offering both quantitative and qualitative insight into how the field is evolving. As such, the annual publication trend demonstrated a marked and sustained growth in scholarly output over the past five years, reflecting not only an intensified research effort but also the diversification of hydrogel-based implant applications across multiple biomedical disciplines (**Figure S1A**, Supporting Information). Complementary keyword co-occurrence mapping, conducted with VOSviewer, revealed how research priorities have shifted toward multifunctional, precision-engineered materials, highlighting the field’s trajectory toward more sophisticated and application-specific solutions (Figure S1B, Supporting Information). Notably, clusters related to “wearable devices,” “skin,” and “regeneration” reflect application-driven research, whereas terms such as “high conductivity,” “nanomaterial,” and “bioink” highlight material and fabrication strategies. The overlay visualization additionally encodes the average year of appearance for each keyword, illustrating a temporal shift in research focus. Newer trends, shown in shades of yellow and orange, point toward smart and multifunctional hydrogels for biosensing and personalized medicine. Together, these findings establish a clear rationale for this review: the accelerated growth and thematic evolution of IHG research demand an updated, integrative synthesis.

Thus, herein, we consolidate core design principles with a critical appraisal of translational challenges, providing a comprehensive overview of multifunctional IHGs. Special emphasis is given to fabrication and design strategies—particularly those enabled by advanced 3D and 4D printing technologies—and their applications in four primary domains: (i) hydrogel coatings for

implants via covalent and noncovalent attachment; (ii) injectable hydrogels for infection control; (iii) scaffolds for bone regeneration tailored to biological performance requirements; and (iv) hydrogels for health monitoring systems (**Figure 1**). Importantly, this work distinguishes itself from earlier literature by offering an integrative perspective that spans antimicrobial coatings, injectable formulations, bone-regenerative scaffolds, and biosensing platforms. It underscores the clinical impact of structural dynamics achieved through additive manufacturing and highlights advances in covalent and noncovalent surface modifications for infection prevention and stimuli-responsive drug delivery. Furthermore, it extends the discussion to regulatory considerations, preclinical evaluation models, and the latest innovations in smart hydrogels for personalized medicine and real-time health monitoring. Finally, it addresses key barriers to clinical translation—material stability, biocompatibility, and functional integration—and outlines future directions for next-generation multifunctional IHG systems.

Figure 1. Schematic overview of multifunctional implantable hydrogels (IHGs) and their main application domains. The central circle highlights the integrative role of IHGs in biomedical applications, while the

surrounding segments illustrate key areas covered in this review: additive manufacturing strategies for hydrogel fabrication (top right), including 3D printing and tailored ink formulations; hydrogel coatings for implants via covalent and non-covalent attachment methods; injectable hydrogels for infection control, addressing design, synthesis, and translational aspects; IHGs engineered for bone defect repair with emphasis on osteoconductivity, immunomodulation, and vascularization; and hydrogels designed for real-time health monitoring, including biochemical, physiological, and disease-related parameters. Created with Biorender.com

2. ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING OF IMPLANTABLE HYDROGELS

The employment of additive manufacturing technologies including 3D and 4D printing for the development of implantable hydrogels has made it possible to make highly precise, patient-specific clinical devices for drug delivery and tissue engineering [66]. Recent work documented the utilization of hybrid hydrogels composed of natural polymers: alginate [67], gelatin [68], and hyaluronic acid [69] with their synthetic counterparts, i.e., polyethylene glycol (PEG) and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), to obtain superior mechanical properties (compressive strength > 50 kPa) and regulated degradation rates to match the implant condition [70]. Advances in 3D printing technologies, such as micro extrusion and stereolithography, enable accurate layer-by-layer printing with 50 μm resolution, which is required for the replication of intricate tissue structure [71, 72].

2.1. Hydrogel ink for additive manufacturing

The 3D and 4D printability of hydrogel inks largely depends on their viscosity and shear-thinning behaviour. Hydrogel inks exhibiting viscosities in the range 0.1–10 Pa·s at low shear rates facilitate smooth extrusion through printer nozzles [73]. Alginate-based inks, with a viscosity of approximately 1 Pa·s at a shear rate of 1 s^{-1} , demonstrate excellent extrudability and are widely regarded for their print-friendly rheological properties [74]. Shear-thinning behaviour with values of flow indices between 0.2 and 0.4 ensures smooth extrusion along with structural stability [75]. Rheological properties such as storage modulus (G') and loss modulus (G'') play a key role in layer stacking. Inks, such as gelatin-methacryloyl (GelMA), with a storage modulus greater than 1 kPa—typically ranging from 1 to 5 kPa—demonstrate excellent shape retention [76, 77]. Enhanced gelation kinetics, with a crosslink time of less than 30 seconds, also lend extra structural strength in extrusion-based printing, while low-viscosity inks offer resolutions less than 100 μm in stereolithography [78].

Hydrogel-based ink formulations are designed to address the requirements of specific 3D and 4D printing processes. For extrusion printing, high shear recovery (viscosity recovery >90% in 5 seconds) ensures continuity, and inks containing 3–5 wt % alginate achieve resolutions of around 200 μm for vascular networks [79]. Vat photopolymerization inks typically need low viscosities between 0.01 and 0.1 Pa·s and photoinitiator concentrations of 0.05–0.1 wt%, enabling fast polymerization and the formation of fine microstructures with layer thicknesses of 50–100 μm

[80]. Stimuli-sensitive hydrogels such as PNIPAM enable high-performance 4D printing by achieving programmed deformations with expansion ratios above 300% and activation times under 5 minutes. This rapid, large-scale response allows the creation of dynamic structures for biomedical uses, including drug delivery systems and tissue scaffolds [81].

Figure 2. Additive manufacturing of multimaterial hydrogels including 4D printing and bioprinting with their materials and printing techniques. Created with Biorender.com.

Figure 2 presents a comprehensive summary of multimaterial hydrogel 3D printing techniques and their applications, particularly in bioprinting, 4D printing, and functional hydrogel manufacturing. It presents three dominant 3D printing techniques: Direct-Ink-Writing (DIW), Vat-Switching, and Coaxial Extrusion. DIW, a versatile and widely used technique, enables precise deposition of high-viscosity inks, making it ideal for fabricating complex 3D structures [82]. Although it benefits from technical calibration and compatibility with commercial printers, achieving a balance between ink viscosity and biocompatibility in live cell applications remains challenging [83]. On the other hand, Vat-Switching employs photo-responsive materials to achieve high resolution, making it particularly well-suited for fabricating intricate microarchitectures such as microvascular networks [84]. Coaxial Extrusion stands apart for its ability to facilitate gradient printing with multiple inlets of material, which is of significant use for the fabrication of biomimetic structures, such as cartilage-bone interfaces. Future research should optimize nozzle geometries in Coaxial Extrusion to minimize shear stress and improve cell viability [85].

Bioprinting hydrogels rely on biopolymers, sacrificial materials, and cellular components. Common biopolymers—such as alginate, GelMA, and cellulose—are favored for their biocompatibility and tunable responsiveness. However, these materials often require nanoparticle reinforcement or blending with additional polymers to enhance mechanical properties. For example, blending alginate with cellulose nanocrystals enhances stiffness and biodegradability [86]. Sacrificial substrates—such as gelatin and Pluronic F-127—provide structural support during printing but can exhibit cytotoxicity; safer alternatives include carbohydrate-based inks [87]. Incorporating diverse cell types (e.g., Schwann cells for neural tissue and cardiomyocytes for cardiac patches) highlights bioprinting’s versatility [88]. However, maintaining cell viability and function both during and post printing remains a significant challenge, and approaches such as microenvironmental conditioning during fabrication warrant further investigation.

Advances in 4D printing and PPC hydrogels continue to expand the application of this technology. 4D printing takes advantage of stimuli-responsive polymers like poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) (PNIPAm), polyacrylamide (PAAm), and (poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA)), PAAS (polyacrylate sodium), and CaCl₂ (PAA) as well as crosslinkers like poly(ethylene glycol diacrylate) (PEGDA) and N,N-methylene-bis-acrylamide (MBA) to create constructs with dynamic properties like swelling or shape memory [89]. This technology opens doors to applications in soft robotics, tissue engineering, and self-folding structures. Nevertheless, ensuring long-term material stability in repetitive stimuli is vital for in vivo applications. The incorporation of functional particles—such as MXenes for electrical conductivity—and reinforcing particles—like hydroxyapatite (HAp) for mechanical strength—opens up possibilities for advanced applications in bioelectronics and bone tissue engineering [90]. While these materials introduce valuable functionalities, concerns about their biocompatibility and integration remain. Addressing potential cytotoxicity and improving tissue compatibility through surface modification or the development of biodegradable alternatives will be essential for their safe translation. Collectively, these technologies represent a significant

advance not only in personalized medicine but also in industrial applications, underscoring the need for multidisciplinary approaches to address challenges in scalability and standardization.

2.2. 3D Printing of implantable hydrogels

3D printing via extrusion is founded upon the precise layer-by-layer deposition of hydrogel inks to build structures. However, structural fidelity may be challenging to preserve during printing due to gravitational collapse and uncontrolled ink flow. To overcome such limitations, hydrogels with yield stress above 50 Pa have been developed to enable the ink to sustain shape under self-weight. For example, alginate-based hydrogels reinforced with 2 wt% calcium ions have demonstrated improved printability, maintaining structural fidelity in multilayer constructs up to 20 mm in height [91]. Extrusion pressures between 30–80 kPa and nozzle diameters between 200–400 μm are also optimized to minimize defect formation and facilitate uniform deposition [92].

Printing parameters such as speed, extrusion pressure, and nozzle temperature significantly influence the quality of printed constructs. Low extrusion pressures (<30 kPa) result in incomplete or interrupted layers, while high pressures (>100 kPa) result in over-extrusion and smearing [93]. Studies have shown that printing speeds of 5–10 mm/s offer the best balance between resolution and consistency of deposition [94]. Temperature-controlled extrusion is particularly important for thermosensitive hydrogels like GelMA, where 37–40 °C nozzle temperatures are kept constant to allow free flow without pre-gelation [95, 96]. These optimized parameters enable the fabrication of complex geometries, such as porous scaffolds with over 85% interconnectivity, which are crucial for effective tissue integration.

Print resolution in extrusion-based techniques is governed by nozzle diameter, rheological properties of the hydrogel, and extrusion pressure. High printing precision is particularly critical for applications such as vascular scaffolds, where pore sizes range of 200–400 μm are necessary to facilitate cell infiltration and nutrient diffusion [97]. High resolution has been facilitated by new nozzle designs, such as tapered nozzles, which have reduced filament diameters to as small as 100 μm . Moreover, shear-thinning hydrogel inks with a flow index value between 0.3 and 0.5 enable more controlled extrusion, achieving printing resolutions below 200 μm without compromising mechanical stability [98]. These advances make extrusion-based printing viable for complicated biomedical constructs. Post-printing crosslinking processes are required for enhancing the mechanical behavior and stability of hydrogel constructs without sacrificing their biological compatibility. Ionic crosslinking with divalent cations (e.g., calcium ions) has been widely employed for alginate-based hydrogels, achieving 20–30 kPa compressive strengths [99]. When compared to pure GelMA hydrogels (18–21 kPa), the hybrid inks showed a greater compressive modulus (25–28.35 kPa) [100]. Dual crosslinking strategies, combining ionic and covalent mechanisms, further increase structural integrity, with storage moduli above 2 kPa, for long-term performance under physiological conditions [101].

Leveraging these improvements in print resolution and mechanical stability, extrusion-based techniques now support the development of hybrid composite scaffolds tailored for advances in tissue engineering. These are complex, multilayered structures designed for tissue engineering applications. They comprise a non-plastic bioink for cell incorporation and a plastic support ink to ensure mechanical strength and structural fidelity [102]. The bioink, composed of hydrogels, can facilitate cell adhesion, growth, and differentiation due to their biocompatibility and biomimicry. Conversely, the ink used for plastic support, which is typically sourced from thermoplastics such as PCL or polylactic acid (PLA), provides the mechanical integrity required to support the architecture of the scaffold on fabrication and subsequently in biological applications. The layer-by-layer arrangement allows precise spatial control over bioactive and structural components, facilitating the introduction of biomimetic gradients or zonal architectures that closely resemble native tissue. Such material integration exploits the complementary properties of each ink to enable applications in regenerative medicine, namely in load-bearing tissues or complex organs with both biological function and mechanical strength. For instance, Shim et al. [103] employed PCL and chondrocyte cell-encapsulated alginate hydrogel in alternating layers to successfully 3D bioprint a multi-layer, cell-laden, and cytocompatible composite-structure material using a multiple head deposition system, resulting in an effective cartilage reconstruction in a murine model. The vitality of the chondrocytes was little affected by the printing process. This technology facilitated the fabrication of distinct pre-tissue constructs by simultaneously streamlining scaffold formation and enabling the accurate deposition of cells and growth factors at defined locations. Histochemical analyses conducted four weeks post-implantation revealed enhanced cartilage tissue formation and increased type II collagen fibril formation within the 3D-printed PCL–alginate scaffold, with no evidence of adverse tissue reaction. Therefore, the fabrication of multilayered structures through 3D printing holds significant potential in tissue engineering, advancing both technological capabilities and the material versatility of hydrogel-based systems.

3. HYDROGEL COATINGS FOR IMPLANTS

While hydrogels hold significant promise as implantable biomaterials, several challenges hinder their clinical use as standalone implants. A primary limitation is their inherent mechanical weakness—characterized by low strength and limited load-bearing capacity—which renders them unsuitable for applications demanding robust structural integrity such as bone or joint replacements [104]. Many implantable hydrogels also degrade over time via either hydrolysis or enzymatic reactions, which can result in a premature loss of function before fulfilling their intended purpose [105, 106]. Another concern is the poor fixation and integration of the implantable hydrogels within the body, as they often lack the rigidity to anchor effectively within tissues, leading to displacement or failure over time [107]. To overcome these challenges, hydrogel coatings have been developed to combine the inherent biocompatibility of hydrogels with the mechanical robustness of implants, thereby forming a solid–hydrogel hybrid platform. In such materials, the underlying implant provides the required structural integrity, while the top hydrogel layer enhances biocompatibility, cell adhesion, promotes tissue integration, and reduces immune

response [108-111]. Hydrogel coatings can also be engineered for localized and controlled delivery of drugs and biological agents at the implant site, thereby minimizing systemic adverse effects and further enhancing surface biocompatibility [108, 109, 111]. This section reviews the strategies employed for the attachment of hydrogel coatings, as well as the types of hydrogel coatings utilized—particularly those aimed at preventing implant-induced infections. Current challenges associated with the application of hydrogel coatings and potential future directions in this field are also discussed.

3.1. Strategies for surface attachment of hydrogel coatings

3.1.1. Noncovalent attachment

The non-covalent attachment of hydrogel coatings relies on intermolecular interactions between hydrogel macromolecules and the implant surface, rather than chemical bonding, leading to a reversible and dynamic surface modification. Electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions [112-114], hydrogen bonding [115-118], and van der Waals forces [118] are usually involved in the non-covalent attachment of hydrogel coatings. Such methods do not require complex chemical modifications or harsh reaction conditions, preserving the structure and properties of the hydrogels. Common strategies include physical entrapment [119-121], adsorption-driven deposition (physisorption) [112-114, 118], electrostatic self-assembly [122, 123], and layer-by-layer (LbL) assembly [124-127]. This section explores non-covalent attachment methods and their underlying mechanisms for fabricating hydrogel coatings on the surfaces of implants.

In physical entrapment, also known as mechanical interlocking, hydrogel macromolecules are entrapped within the surface topographical features such as micro-grooves, pores, or interwoven structures, without any chemical bonding as illustrated in **Figure 3A**. For example, poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS) sheets featuring surface micro-protrusions and microbridge structures were coated with a PVA hydrogel through interfacial mechanical interlocking [119]. A 90° peeling test conducted on both flat and microstructured PDMS substrates to assess the adhesion strength of the PVA hydrogel indicated a significantly higher adhesive force on the microbridge-structured surfaces compared to the flat ones. This enhanced adhesion can be attributed to the increased contact area and mechanical resistance offered by the microfeatures, which physically restrict the movement and detachment of the hydrogel network. Porous titanium surfaces have also been physically coated with poly(acrylic acid)-based hydrogels, facilitated by their inherent surface porosity [120]. However, in most cases, implant surfaces lack the necessary topographical features for effective entrapment of hydrogel macromolecules, necessitating additional surface pre-treatments.

Anodic oxidation, or anodization, an electrochemical process, is predominantly used to create surface topographical features by forming an oxide layer on the metallic substrates [128-130]. This method enhances surface roughness, porosity, and chemical properties, improving the physical interlocking of hydrogel coatings. For instance, a recent study used anodization to construct

different surface nanostructures on pure titanium substrates to physically attach PAAm hydrogel coating[121]. Distinct nanostructures, like nanopores, nanotubes, and punch-through nanotubes, were created on the anodized Ti surface (ATS) by changing the oxidation voltage (set at 10, 20, or 30 V). Then, PAAm hydrogel solution with different ratios of monomer to cross-linker (N,N,N',N'-tetramethylethylenediamine) were applied to the surface to obtain a hydrogel coating with varying modulus (from soft to stiff) via in situ radical polymerization and nano-mechanical interlocking. Lab shear test, as well as repeated twisting and bending stability evaluations after swelling in water for 24 hours, showed a strong adhesion between the hydrogel and ATS. The highest adhesion strength was observed on ATS with punch-through nanotubes, which was assigned to the high contact area at the surface/the hydrogel coating interface. Such an increase in the contact surface area can result in more interfacial nano-mechanical interlocking, further acting as mechanically-active adhesion sites [121]. In addition to anodization, techniques such as micro-milling [131], laser processing, and laser ablation [132] can be employed to generate surface topographical features that facilitate the mechanical entrapment of hydrogel coatings.

Physical entrapment offers a simple and reliable strategy for the non-covalent immobilization of hydrogel coatings. However, the stability and durability of such coatings under harsh physiological conditions are generally limited. Moreover, successful physical entrapment requires the implant surface to either possess inherent microtextures or be deliberately engineered to facilitate the interlocking of hydrogel chains, which further constrains the clinical applicability of this approach. Adsorption-driven deposition, or physisorption, results from weak intermolecular-forces such as van der Waals and hydrophobic interactions, hydrogen and ionic bonding to attach hydrogel coatings onto implant surfaces. Van der Waals forces are created between the hydrogel polymeric chains and the surface due to temporary dipoles, which are momentary fluctuations in electron distribution within atoms or molecules, resulting in a reversible attachment of hydrogel coatings [118]. Hydrophobic interactions between the hydrophobic segments of the hydrogel polymers and nonpolar regions of the surface can also facilitate the non-covalent attachment of the hydrogel coatings [112]. For instance, a Janus-structured hydrogel containing hydrophobic lignin domains was applied to various substrates (e.g., glass, metal, rubber) through aggregation and surface hydrophobic interactions [112]. Hydrogen bonding of hydrogels can also occur when hydrogen atoms in functional groups (e.g., hydroxyl (-OH), amine (-NH₂)) on either the surface or within the hydrogel structure interact with electronegative atoms (e.g., oxygen, nitrogen) on the other counterpart (i.e., surface or hydrogel) [115-117]. For instance, silicon hydroxide (Si-OH) groups on a silicon wafer can form hydrogen bonds with either -OH or -NH₂ groups in chitosan (**Figure 3B**), which is a natural polysaccharide with abundant -OH and -NH₂ groups in its structure [133].

Electrostatic self-assembly and LbL assembly to attach hydrogel coatings rely on the electrostatic forces between oppositely charged molecules or surfaces. In electrostatic self-assembly (**Figure 3C**), a hydrogel containing charged functional groups (e.g., -NH₃⁺ in chitosan, or carboxyl (-COO⁻) and sulphate (-SO₄⁻) groups in alginate) interacts with an oppositely charged surface, leading to

spontaneous and reversible adhesion [114, 123]. LbL assembly (**Figure 3D**), however, is a stepwise, alternating deposition of oppositely charged polyelectrolytes to form a multilayer-coating [134-136]. In hydrogel coatings, a positively charged polymer (e.g., chitosan) is adsorbed onto a negatively charged surface, then a negatively charged polymer (e.g., alginate) is deposited as the second layer. With consecutive repeats, a hydrogel coating with multi layers is deposited on the surface [124, 135, 137]. For example, in a recent study, LbL deposition of polyvinylamine (PVAm) and dopamine-modified hyaluronic acid (HA-DN) was achieved via electrostatic interactions between two polymeric layers on different substrates such as gold, glass, stainless steel, and polyvinyl chloride (PVC) [137]. As shown in **Figure 3E**, each layer was deposited on the surface by successive dip immersion of the substrate in the polymeric solutions, resulting in a coating with alternating layers of PVAm and HA-DN (**Figure 3F**). Water contact angle measurements and bacterial adhesion tests confirmed effective polymer adhesion; however, the absence of surface pre-treatment prior to coating deposition on these non-reactive substrates raises concerns regarding the long-term stability and uniformity of the polymeric layers.

While electrostatic interactions between oppositely charged polymers allow for simple and effective multilayer hydrogel construction, they can lead to delamination or layer separation under specific conditions. For instance, a study found that variations in pH and ionic strength of the incubation milieu induce swelling and structural changes in chitosan/alginate multilayer films, disrupting the electrostatic equilibrium and leading to interfacial delamination [138]. Similarly, Chehreara et al. [139] demonstrated that alginate–chitosan multilayers maintained mechanical stability in acidic fluids but dissolved gradually in neutral environments, confirming pH-dependent strength of electrostatic interactions. The same phenomenon can happen for a hydrogel-coated implant in the physiological environment, where changes in local pH or ionic concentration—such as during inflammation or tissue remodeling—may weaken electrostatic interactions and compromise coating integrity. Electrodeposition has also been used to attach hydrogel coatings via assembly of polymeric chains onto an electrode surface [140, 141]. Electrodeposition involves the migration of charged ions in a solution toward an oppositely charged electrode, which undergoes electron transfer and metallic bonding to the surface [142, 143]. Building on this principle, Zhao et al. [140] coated a chitosan hydrogel incorporating ibuprofen-loaded mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) on a titanium substrate via electrodeposition. As shown in **Figure 3G**, the drug was first loaded into the MSNs, which were then dispersed in the chitosan solution. Subsequently, a titanium plate (serving as the cathode) and a platinum wire were placed in the hydrogel solution, and a negative voltage was applied to the titanium substrate. This process induced the sol–gel transition of chitosan and its deposition on the cathode surface, driven by electrochemical water electrolysis and the resulting localized pH gradient [140]. In another study, a hybrid hydrogel coating of alkynyl chitosan and chitosan was fabricated on stainless steel wires via electrodeposition from a solution containing both components and a platinum foil as anode [141].

Figure 3. Non-covalent attachment strategies. Schematic illustrations of A) mechanical interlocking of a hydrogel coating, B) hydrogen bonding, C) electrostatic self-assembly, and D) layer by layer (LbL) assembly. All created in Biorender.com with permission. E) Fabrication steps of a coating from polyvinylamine (PVAm) and dopamine-modified hyaluronic acid (HA-DN) polymers by LbL assembly and F) schematic of the coating with successive layers of PVAm and HA-DN. Reproduced with permission [137]. Copyright 2020, Elsevier. G) Electrodeposition of a chitosan hydrogel incorporating ibuprofen (IB)-loaded mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) on a titanium plate. Reproduced with permission [140]. Copyright 2014, Elsevier.

The successful surface attachment of hydrogel coating is usually assessed via surface characterization techniques such as Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) to confirm the presence of specific functional groups associated with the hydrogel layer [127, 144-146]. Microscopy techniques and contact angle measurements have also been used to confirm the presence of hydrogel coating on the surface [114, 124, 147]. However, non-covalent attachment of hydrogel coatings exhibits drawbacks and limitations such as weak coating adhesion and sensitivity to environmental conditions. Non-covalent interactions (e.g., hydrophobic forces, hydrogen bonding) are inherently weaker than covalent bonding, resulting in potential delamination under physiological conditions. In addition, electrostatically attached and physisorbed hydrogel coatings are susceptible to environmental changes, making them prone to detachment under variations in pH or mechanical stress [124, 127]. This instability significantly limits their long-term clinical applications, particularly in medical implants subjected to dynamic physiological environments.

In load-bearing applications such as femoral and dental implants, hydrogel–solid interfaces are typically subjected to substantial mechanical loading, including shear, compressive, and tensile stresses throughout both implantation and functional use [148]. During surgical insertion, these implants experience large shear and compressive forces that can critically challenge the adhesive

integrity between the hydrogel coating and the underlying substrate [148, 149]. When the adhesion strength is insufficient—particularly in systems relying on non-covalent interactions—premature delamination of the hydrogel layer may occur even during implantation. Furthermore, dental and orthopedic implants are exposed to continuous cyclic micromovements caused by mastication and locomotion, respectively [150]. These repetitive dynamic forces can progressively degrade the interface, compromising hydrogel adhesion over time and ultimately leading to coating failure and loss of function.

Covalent attachment strategies, which will be discussed in the following subsection, offer a promising route to strengthen the bond between hydrogel coatings and implant surfaces. By forming stable covalent anchors, these methods help reduce the risk of coating failure when the implant is exposed to mechanical stress. Regardless of the bonding approach used, it is essential to include mechanical testing—such as scratch tests, lap shear assessments, and fatigue loading simulations—as part of the evaluation process [121, 151, 152]. These tests help ensure that the hydrogel coatings can perform reliably under the types of forces they will encounter in the body [121, 152]. Taking these factors into account allows for the development of more robust hydrogel-coated implants that are better suited for the complex mechanical environment of real-world clinical use.

3.1.2. Covalent bonding

Covalent bonding of hydrogels involves permanent chemical linkages between the hydrogel and the surface, resulting in a robust coating with long-term stability, durability, and resistance to delamination under physiological conditions. Strategies developed for the covalent immobilization of hydrogels include Schiff base reactions [153, 154], Michael addition [155, 156], click chemistry [157-160], silane coupling [161-163], surface-initiated polymerization [145, 164-168], and plasma-induced attachment or grafting [167, 169, 170], each with specific mechanisms explained in this section.

Covalent attachment of hydrogels can be achieved via reactions between the functional groups on the substrate surface and those in the chemical structure of hydrogels. For covalent attachment using a Schiff base reaction (**Figure 4A**), primary amine ($-NH_2$) groups in the hydrogel structure (e.g., in chitosan or gelatin) react with an aldehyde ($-CHO$) or ketone ($-C=O$)-functionalized surface, resulting in a dynamic imine ($-C=N$) bond. Then, the formed $-C=N$ groups can be reduced into a stable secondary amine ($-C-NH-$) bond, which is irreversible, using $NaBH_4$ or $NaCNBH_3$. For example, a hybrid hydrogel composed of chitosan (CS) and polydopamine (PDA) was attached covalently onto PMMA substrates functionalized with aldehyde groups [153]. Schiff base reactions between the amine groups of either CS or pDA and $-CHO$ functionalities resulted in a robustly adherent hydrogel coating. If more stable covalent linkages are required, carbodiimide chemistry, primarily using EDC (1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide) and NHS (N-hydroxysuccinimide) can be used as a complementary step. In carbodiimide chemistry, EDC/NHS

is used to convert carboxyl (-COOH) groups on the hydrogel or substrate into an amine-reactive NHS ester that subsequently reacts with -NH₂ groups, forming an irreversible amide (-CONH-) bond [171, 172].

Michael addition, as a fast and irreversible reaction, occurs between a nucleophile and an electron-deficient α , β -unsaturated carbonyl compound under physiological conditions [155, 156]. In hydrogels, covalent binding occurs when a soft nucleophile, such as a thiol (-SH) or amine (-NH₂) group—present either on the surface or within the hydrogel structure—attacks the electron-deficient C=C double bond of acrylate- or maleimide-functionalized surfaces or polymers. Such a reaction can result in a strong C-C or C-N bond, permanently linking the hydrogel to the surface as illustrated in **Figure 4B**. Click chemistry encompasses three highly efficient and selective reaction types that enable covalent modification of biomaterials, which are highly efficient and selective for covalent modification of biomaterials, with applicability to robustly attach hydrogel coatings to implants. The first one is azide-alkyne cycloaddition, in which one component (i.e., hydrogel or surface) can be functionalized with azide (-N₃), and the other with an alkyne (-C \equiv C). Then, these functional groups undergo a Cu(I)-catalyzed Huisgen 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition, forming a stable bond between two components [173, 174]. The second approach of click chemistry is strain-promoted azide-alkyne cycloaddition with a similar mechanism to the azide-alkyne cycloaddition, but using strained cyclooctyne instead of a copper catalyst to avoid cytotoxic Cu(I) [175, 176]. The most prominent click chemistry mechanism (known as thiol-ene click reaction) is based on the reactions between a thiol (-SH) group (either on the surface or hydrogel structure) and an alkene (-C=C) group under UV light or a radical initiator [158-160]. As illustrated in **Figure 4C**, UV or thermal initiation generates thiol radicals, which react with the double bond in the ene group through a radical-mediated process, forming a covalent carbon-sulfur (C-S) bond. For example, in the coating of single-component or hybrid hydrogels composed of PNIPAM and poly(acrylic acid) onto various substrates—such as silicon wafers, glass, and gold—the substrate surfaces were first functionalized with thiol groups. Subsequently, ene-functionalized polymers, along with a dithioerythritol cross-linker, were spin-coated onto the surfaces, resulting in coatings of varying thicknesses [160]. In another study, an ene-functionalized hydrogel based on poly(sulfobetaine methacrylate-acrylate acid-2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate) (P(SBMA-AA-HEMA) was covalently attached to thiol-functionalized silicon wafers, showing strong adhesion to the substrate [159].

Silane coupling of hydrogels, which is particularly applicable on inorganic surfaces (such as glass, silicon, and metals), is based on functional silane molecules, containing hydrolysable groups (e.g., alkoxy or chloro groups) and reactive functional groups (e.g., amine, epoxy, or methacrylate) [161-163, 177, 178]. The coupling starts with the hydrolysis of the hydrolysable groups of silane (e.g., Si-OR) and subsequent formation of silanol groups (Si-OH). Then, these Si-OH groups undergo condensation reactions with substrate hydroxyl groups and form strong siloxane (Si-O-Si) bonds, anchoring the silane molecules to the surface. Once silane is covalently attached to the surface, the

reactive end of the silane molecule can react with the hydrogel precursor molecules, resulting in their covalent attachment. Such functional group reactions can differ, depending on the end reactive groups of silane molecules and the hydrogel functional groups. For example, aminosilane (-NH₂) reaction can occur if an aminosilane (e.g., 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane, APTES) with amine (-NH₂) groups is used as the silane-based molecule [163]. In this case, as shown in **Figure 4D**, -NH₂ groups on the silanized surface react with either epoxy, carboxyl (via carbodiimide (EDC/NHS) chemistry), or aldehydes (via Schiff base reaction) groups on the polymeric chains, based on the chemical structure of the hydrogel [163, 179]. Epoxysilane (-epoxy) reactions can also result in the covalent attachment of hydrogels via the interactions between epoxysilane groups on the surface and amine or thiol functionalities of the polymeric chains [161]. Isocyanato (-NCO)-functionalized silanes can also react with -OH or -NH₂ groups on the hydrogel polymeric chains to form urethane or urea linkages [180, 181], which can be leveraged to covalently attach hydrogel coating to a silanized surface. Silane coupling was used to covalently immobilize hydrogel coating on different substrates. For instance, two hydrogels based on either PAAm or PEGDA were coated on porous substrates, including glass, silicon wafers, ceramics, titanium, and aluminum [163]. Prior to hydrogel coating, substrate surfaces were modified using 3-(Trimethoxysilyl)propyl methacrylate (TMSPMA) as the silane coupling agent. Interfacial toughness measurements showed strong adhesion of the hydrogel coating to all pre-silanized substrates, which was attributed to the covalent anchoring of the hydrogel's long-chain polymer networks to the surface [163]. In a recent study, a hybrid hydrogel composed of crosslinked four-armed PEG (starPEG) and heparin was applied to (CoCr) vascular stents that underwent a dual treatment involving silanization and poly(ethylene-alt-maleic anhydride) (PEMA) [177]. The hydrogel coating exhibited mechanical stability under post-ethanol dehydration and stent expansion due to the covalent attachment points provided by silanization and surface hydrophilicity from PEMA treatment, ensuring robust hydrogel adhesion to the stent surface [177]. A gelatin composite hydrogel (GMP) was used to coat different medical device surfaces, including artificial joints, catheters, and titanium alloys via surface pre-silanization using a silane coupling agent possessing an unsaturated double bond [178]. This agent was grafted onto a co-deposited layer of PDA and polyethyleneimine (PEI), facilitating covalent bonding between the hydrogel and the substrate. The hydrogel coating withstands rigorous stability evaluations such as ultrasonic treatment and sustained underwater shearing [178].

Surface initiated polymerization (SIP) and grafting of hydrogel coatings, which is the most prominent approach to covalently attach hydrogels, involves simultaneous polymerization and covalent binding of hydrogel polymeric chains on the surface [145, 164-168]. In this method, the substrate surface is pre-activated to introduce functional groups that serve as initiation sites for polymerization, allowing simultaneous polymer chain growth and surface grafting (**Figure 4E**). Polymerization mechanism of hydrogel precursors (monomers) can be based on either atom transfer radical polymerization (ATRP) [182, 183], reversible addition-fragmentation chain transfer (RAFT) [184, 185], or photopolymerization [169, 186]. SIP enables a controlled formation

of thin hydrogel films with tunable properties such as thickness, crosslinking density, and functionality. For example, the surface of PVC substrates was initially activated with benzophenone, then, a hydrogel coating from N, N-dimethylacrylamide was photopolymerized from the surface using UV light and Irgacure as the photoinitiator [164]. The coated sample was exposed to continuous saline flow for 12 hours, during which the coating retained its thickness, indicating strong surface adhesion [164]. A hydrogel coating from PNIPAM-incorporated with zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NP) was also grafted onto silanized glass coverslips by UV irradiation and surface initiated photopolymerization [165]. However, adhesion robustness and long-term stability were not evaluated, leaving the coating's suitability for medical implants uncertain. In another study, a catechol-modified GelMA hydrogel was photo-cross-linked and simultaneously grafted to titanium substrates by UV irradiation [168]. Lap shear tests of the swollen hydrogel coating demonstrated that catechol motifs enhance adhesion strength through strong binding interactions with the titanium surface. Specifically, catechol groups form robust coordination bonds with titanium oxide, thereby improving interfacial adhesion [187]. Furthermore, under oxidative conditions, catechol can establish covalent bonds with surface hydroxyl groups on titanium, resulting in durable and stable adhesion [188].

Electrosynthesis or electropolymerization has also been used to covalently graft hydrogel coatings on various surfaces [145, 166]. This technique, which only applies to conductive surfaces, involves electrochemical oxidation or reduction reactions to generate reactive species that initiate polymerization directly on the substrate. The electrosynthesis of hydrogel coatings typically begins by immersing the substrate—serving as the working electrode—into an electrolyte containing hydrogel monomers and an electrochemical initiator. Then, a voltage is applied to initiate oxidation or reduction reactions, forming reactive species on the substrate that trigger polymerization and formation of a covalently bonded hydrogel network from the surface. To enhance the cross-linking density and mechanical stability of the forming hydrogel, additional cross-linkers can be incorporated into the electrolyte. For example, a polyacrylate-based hydrogel coating was electropolymerized onto titanium implants using ammonium peroxydisulphate as an electrochemical initiator, enabling the integration of silver antimicrobial nanoparticles [166]. In another study, hydrogel coatings from poly (2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate) (PHEMA) and a copolymer of PEGDA and acrylic acid (AA) (PEGDA-AA) were electrosynthesized on titanium substrates [145]. However, the adhesion strength of these electrodeposited hydrogel coatings was not evaluated, leaving their stability under dynamic physiological conditions unverified.

All the wet chemistry methods, such as click chemistry and silane coupling, discussed so far, while effective in fabricating hydrogel coatings on medical implants, have several limitations [189, 190]. These include potential toxicity, inadequate adhesion, complex processing steps, and challenges in controlling coating properties. Click chemistry may suffer from slow reaction rates, byproducts, and reliance on specific functional groups, while silane coupling is prone to *in vivo* degradation and may not replicate native tissue properties. Moreover, the use of organic solvents and harsh

reagents raises concerns about scalability, reproducibility, and biocompatibility due to residual chemicals. Multiple complex steps that require organic solvents or harsh chemicals make the scalability and reproducibility of these methods quite challenging. In addition, potential biocompatibility concerns due to unreacted reagents or by-products hinder their practical application in biomedical settings.

To address these challenges, plasma-based methods have emerged, offering a dry, simple, and environmentally friendly alternative for surface modification before the application of hydrogel coatings. Such solvent-free approaches minimize contamination risks and allow for rapid, tunable modifications in a single-step process, making them highly suitable for biomedical applications [167, 169, 170, 191]. Plasma-induced covalent binding of hydrogel coatings involves surface pre-treatment with low-temperature plasma discharge to introduce reactive functional groups (e.g., -OH, -COOH, -NH₂, or radicals). Such reactive groups are subsequently used to either attach pre-prepared hydrogels or to polymerize directly and graft hydrogel monomers from the plasma-activated surface [167, 169, 170, 191], as illustrated in **Figure 5F**. For example, thin hydrogel layers of PEI, poly(N-vinyl pyrrolidone) (PVP), and poly(acrylic acid) (PAA) were covalently immobilized on poly(tetrafluoroethylene) (PTFE) and poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) substrates using low-pressure argon plasma treatment and via amide bonds between the hydrogels and the surface [192].

In plasma-assisted surface grafting, hydrogel polymeric chains grow and crosslink from monomers pre-immobilized on the surface, resulting in a simultaneous hydrogel formation and covalent bonding onto the surface [167, 169, 170, 191]. For example, a hybrid hydrogel made from quaternized ammonium chitosan and poly(ethylene glycol) methacrylate (PEGMA) was coated on a fluoropolymer substrate that had been pre-activated with peroxides using argon plasma [167]. A cross-linked hydrogel layer formed on the surface as the acrylate/methacrylate groups in the hydrogel solution reacted with both the peroxide-functionalized surface and each other under UV irradiation. Concurrently, the coating was covalently linked to the surface while the hydrogel was crosslinked from the precursor solution. Atmospheric pressure plasma treatment was also used to polymerize and graft acrylate-based hydrogels from hydroxyethyl methacrylate (HEMA) and 2-(diethylamino) ethyl methacrylate (DEAEMA) onto gold screen-printed electrodes via different oxygen- and nitrogen-containing functional groups [193].

Plasma immersion ion implantation (PIII) has also been used to create covalently attached hydrogel coatings on polymeric substrates [170]. In PIII, a negative bias voltage is applied to the substrate, resulting in the acceleration of positively charged ions in the plasma discharge toward the surface and forming free radicals embedded beneath the surface [194, 195]. When in contact with the hydrogel or biomolecules solution, the free radicals, which migrate to the surface, facilitate covalent binding of hydrogel or bioactive molecules to the PIII-treated substrate [170, 196]. For instance, in a recent study, acrylamide and silk-based hydrogels were applied to PTFE substrates pre-treated with PIII to generate surface-embedded radicals [170]. These radicals played

a dual role by initiating spontaneous polymerization of the hydrogel monomers and covalently binding the resulting hydrogels to the surface without additional cross-linking agents or initiators. T-peel mechanical and stability tests showed a strong adhesion between the hydrogel and the PIII-treated PTFE substrate that was attributed to the surface-embedded radicals, facilitating both the hydrogel polymerization and the development of strong covalent links between the hydrogel and the substrate.

Figure 4. Covalent bonding strategies. Schematic illustration of A) Schiff base reactions between an aldehyde-functionalized surface and hydrogel polymeric chains with amine groups, B) Michael addition reactions between a thiol group with unpaired electrons (under oxidative conditions) as the Michael donor and an acrylate-based group on the surface, C) thiol-ene click reactions between thiol and alkene (-C=C) groups under UV or thermal initiation, D) silane coupling mechanism between an aminosilanized surface and hydrogel polymeric chains with carboxyl groups (using carbodiimide chemistry), E) surface initiated polymerization of hydrogel polymeric chains from the surface (grafting), and F) plasma-assisted surface attachment (using functional groups) and polymerization (grafting) of hydrogel coatings. Figure created in Biorender.com with permission.

3.2. Hydrogel coating for implants to prevent infections

Infections associated with biomedical implants remain one of the most challenging complications in modern medicine. Despite improvements in surgical procedures and sterilization practices, up to 5% of implants—particularly orthopedic and dental—still become infected [197]. This risk rises even further in high-risk patients or complex surgical cases [198]. These infections are a leading cause of implant failure and place a heavy burden equally on patients and healthcare systems. Treatment often involves extended hospital stays, prolonged antibiotic use, and costly revision surgeries. In the U.S. alone, the financial burden of orthopedic implant infections is estimated to be in the billions each year [199]. Beyond economic costs, affected patients endure significant pain, reduced mobility, and emotional distress—underscoring the urgent need for infection-preventive strategies in implant design and biomaterial development.

Hydrogel coatings have been used to prevent implant-induced infections by forming a protective barrier against bacterial colonization and biofilm formation, either through their intrinsic properties or by releasing antimicrobial agents incorporated into their hydrophilic polymeric networks [141, 200]. The following section reviews and discusses the most prominent anti-infective hydrogel coatings developed for medical implants, highlighting their key characteristics. A summary of recent studies on these hydrogel coatings, including their immobilization approaches, stability assessments, and results from both in vitro and in vivo biological evaluations are provided in **Table 1**.

Chitosan-based hydrogel coatings are among the most widely investigated natural materials, recognized for their intrinsic antibacterial and anti-infective properties [200, 201]. As a cationic biopolymer derived from the deacetylation of chitin, chitosan carries a positive charge at physiological pH due to the presence of protonated amino ($-NH_2$) groups. This positive charge facilitates electrostatic interactions with the negatively charged microbial cell membranes, leading to membrane disruption and subsequent inhibition of microbial growth [202]. Building on these properties, chitosan-based hydrogels—either as single-component systems [141, 200] or in combination with other polymers—have been employed as coatings for medical implants [203, 204]. For example, a composite hydrogel coating composed of chitosan and alkynyl-functionalized chitosan was applied to a stainless-steel substrate via electrophoretic co-deposition, demonstrating effective antibacterial activity against both *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) [141]. The antibacterial performance was evaluated through in vitro assays, including bacterial adhesion tests and zone of inhibition measurements, which confirmed a significant reduction in bacterial colonization. However, the study did not assess the stability or long-term antibacterial performance of the hydrogel coating under conditions that mimic the physiological environment. In addition, while the results highlight the potential of electrophoretically deposited chitosan-based hydrogels for infection control, further validation in more complex, translational models, including in vivo studies, is essential to determine their clinical relevance and durability.

In another study, two different chitosan-based (CHI) hydrogel coatings cross-linked using either genipin (Ti-CHIGP) or PEG (Ti-CHIPEG) were applied to titanium implants via surface grafting combined with EDC/NHS chemistry [200]. Hydrolytic and enzymatic degradation assays, conducted in both the absence and presence of lysozyme, showed that the Ti-CHIGP hydrogel coating exhibited a lower degradation rate compared to Ti-CHIPEG. This difference was attributed to the more compact polymeric network formed by genipin-induced crosslinking in Ti-CHIGP, which enhances structural stability and confers greater resistance to enzymatic degradation. Both hydrogels exhibited multifunctional antibacterial potential, exhibiting bacteria-repelling properties as well as contact killing effects of *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, as illustrated in **Figure 5A**. These antibacterial properties were assessed using live/dead bacterial staining assays, where bacterial suspensions were incubated with the coated surfaces for 24 hours, followed by staining with SYTO9 and propidium iodide to differentiate between live (green) and dead (red) bacteria. Fluorescence microscopy images and quantitative analysis showed a significantly higher proportion of dead bacteria on the hydrogel-coated samples compared to uncoated controls. The better antibacterial activity of the developed hydrogel coatings against *E. coli* was related to the thinner bacterial wall and its more susceptibility to be disturbed by the chitosan hydrogel coating. In vivo subcutaneous implantation of hydrogel-coated and uncoated Ti6Al4V implants in rats demonstrated that chitosan-based hydrogel coatings—particularly Ti-CHIPEG—elicited a milder tissue response as verified by histological scores. Combined with their strong in vitro antibacterial performance, these hydrogel coatings exhibit dual functionality, offering effective infection prevention and improved tissue compatibility for biomedical implant applications [200]. However, despite the inclusion of in vivo data, the infection model was not challenged with live bacteria, limiting the conclusions that can be drawn about the in vivo anti-microbial efficacy of the coatings.

Polyacrylamide (polyAM)-based hydrogel coatings have also been extensively utilized in developing anti-infective surfaces for medical implants, due to their biocompatibility and tailorable physicochemical attributes [164, 165]. Their high water content contributes to resistance against protein adsorption and bacterial adhesion, inhibiting bacterial colonization and biofilm formation [205]. In this context, an acrylamide-based hydrogel coating was applied to PVC and silicone tubes via surface-initiated polymerization of N,N-dimethylacrylamide (DMAA) monomers, using Irgacure as the photoinitiator [164]. The ultrathin hydrogel coating exhibited strong antifouling properties by forming a highly hydrated surface that physically prevented protein adsorption and bacterial attachment. Its antibacterial performance was assessed in vitro using a genetically engineered *E. coli* strain expressing green-fluorescent protein (GFP) for a straightforward visualization [206]. Under static conditions, hydrogel-coated and uncoated flat samples were incubated with the bacterial culture for 4 hours at 37 °C. A dynamic flow model was also employed to mimic physiological environments, where *E. coli* suspensions were circulated through coated and uncoated tubing using a peristaltic pump for 8 hours at 37 °C. After static and dynamic incubation, samples were rinsed with PBS and examined using fluorescence microscopy. Quantitative image analysis (**Figure 5B**) showed a marked reduction in bacterial adhesion on the

hydrogel-coated surfaces under both static and flow conditions—even in the absence of any antibiotic release—highlighting the coating's robust passive antibacterial function. [164]. In vivo implantation studies were conducted in a porcine iliac artery model to further assess the hydrogel coating's performance under physiological conditions. Medical-grade silicone tubes—either uncoated or hydrogel-coated—were surgically inserted into the iliac arteries of anesthetized pigs (Guanxi Ba-ma) and monitored via Doppler ultrasound, which is commonly used to track real-time blood flow velocity and determine the time to complete occlusion caused by thrombus formation in preclinical settings [207]. The hydrogel-coated tubes exhibited a 60% increase in occlusion time compared to uncoated controls, indicating a delay in clot formation. This suggests that the developed hydrogel coating not only helps reduce early bacterial colonization but also provides resistance to thrombus formation in blood-contacting environments, reinforcing its potential for use in cardiovascular implant applications. However, while the study included both in vitro and in vivo experiments, the in vivo model was short-term and did not involve any bacterial challenge during implantation. Therefore, although the coating demonstrated promising antifouling and thromboresistant properties, its actual anti-infective performance under clinically relevant, infection-prone conditions remains to be fully validated. Further long-term implantation and pathogen exposure studies will be necessary to fully characterize the coating's infection-prevention capabilities.

In another study, a thermoresponsive PNIPAM hydrogel layer incorporating ZnO NPs was fabricated on glass substrates via photopolymerization at various thicknesses [165]. The hydrogel-coated surfaces exhibited sustained release of ZnO NPs, which significantly reduced colony-forming units (CFUs) in bacterial culture assays. This antibacterial activity was primarily attributed to the decomposition of ZnO nanoparticles, resulting in the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which was shown to oxidatively damage the bacterial membranes [208]. The antibacterial performance of the developed hydrogel coating was evaluated entirely through in vitro assays, where *E. coli* suspensions were incubated on coated glass surfaces for 24 hours, followed by serial dilution and CFU quantification to determine viable bacterial counts. However, the used experimental setup did not account for dynamic flow conditions or include any assessment of compatibility with mammalian cells—both of which are important for evaluating real-world implant performance.

Hybrid hydrogels, which combine two or more polymers, have also been explored as coatings to prevent implant-related infections [145, 167, 179, 209]. One example is a hydrogel coating derived from ϵ -poly-L-lysine-graft-methacrylamide (EPL-MA), applied to plastic substrates via plasma-assisted grafting. [169]. This coating demonstrated broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity, effectively inhibiting Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus*) as well as fungal pathogens (*Candida albicans*, *Fusarium solani*)—making it one of the few studies to assess both bacterial and fungal models. The antimicrobial properties were attributed to EPL's ability to disrupt microbial membranes [209], leading to cell death. The coating's antimicrobial

performance was evaluated entirely through in vitro assays, including microbial viability tests and CFU quantification following incubation on coated versus uncoated surfaces. However, no in vivo or clinical investigations were performed, and all testing was conducted under static conditions, limiting the ability to predict its effectiveness in dynamic or physiological environments.

In a separate investigation, a hydrogel composed of PEG diacrylate, and acrylic acid (PEGDA-AA) was coated onto titanium substrates via electrosynthesis, with ciprofloxacin (CIP) incorporated either during or after the electrodeposition process [145]. CIP is a broad-spectrum fluoroquinolone antibiotic, commonly used to treat different bacterial infections, caused by Gram-negative and some Gram-positive bacteria [210]. The resulting CIP-loaded hydrogel coating effectively inhibited methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), a clinically significant and drug-resistant pathogen [211]. The antibacterial activity was attributed to the hydrogel's ability to retain and release high amounts of CIP, aided by the anionic acrylic acid components, which enhance drug loading and promote sustained diffusion through ionic interactions with positively charged drug molecules [212]. The antibacterial efficacy was assessed using in vitro methods, including agar diffusion (zone of inhibition) assays and direct-contact bacterial viability tests, all conducted under static conditions and limited to a single bacterial species.

Another hybrid hydrogel coating, composed of PEG and chitosan with different ratios (referred as CS/PEG), was applied onto stainless-steel (archwire, AW) substrates via silane chemistry and subsequent copolymerization specifically for dental implant applications [179]. The resulting coating demonstrated dual functionality, effectively resisting initial bacterial adhesion while actively suppressing *Streptococcus mutans* (UA159) colony formation. The antifouling effect was confirmed through fluorescence microscopy and quantification of in-vitro bacterial adhesion, revealing a substantial reduction in *S. mutans* attachment on coated versus uncoated samples. As shown in **Figure 5C**, the hydrogel-coated archwires exhibited an 88% decrease in bacterial surface coverage, highlighting the strong anti-adhesive capability of the PEG-rich layer. Among the different formulations tested, the highest antibacterial performance was achieved at a chitosan-to-PEG ratio of 0.1:1. This enhanced effect was referred to the optimal concentration of chitosan, which allowed for sufficient antimicrobial activity without compromising the hydrogel's structural integrity or antifouling function. The antimicrobial activity was further supported by 7-day CFU count assays, shown in **Figure 5D**, where bacterial proliferation was significantly suppressed on chitosan-containing hydrogels. CFU counts dropped from approximately 9.3×10^5 on uncoated surfaces to 1.1×10^5 on the hydrogel-coated ones—a reduction of nearly 90% in viable colonies—demonstrating strong bacteriostatic or bactericidal action. These findings align with the dual-mechanism model illustrated in **Figure 5E**, where the PEG component creates a hydrophilic, non-fouling barrier that minimizes bacterial adhesion, while chitosan delivers antimicrobial effects through electrostatic interactions that disrupt bacterial membranes.

In another related work, a hybrid hydrogel coating based on dimethyldecylammonium chitosan (with high quaternization)-graft-poly (ethylene glycol) methacrylate (DMDC-Q-g-EM) was coated on a fluoropolymer substrate by surface-initiated polymerization [167]. The developed DMDC-Q-g-EM showed in vitro antimicrobial activity against various bacteria including *P. aeruginosa*, *E. coli*, and *S. aureus*, as well as fungi (e.g., *F. solani*) by reducing their viability via contact-killing properties. It was postulated that the hydrogel acts as an “anion sponge”, that sucks out some parts of the anionic microbe membrane into the hydrogel porous network structure, as shown in **Figure 5F-H**, resulting in the microbial membrane disruption, eventually killing the microbe.

While numerous studies have reported promising antibacterial effects of hydrogel coatings, a common limitation in the current literature is the predominant use of single-species biofilm models, typically involving well-characterized strains such as *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, or *S. mutans*. Although these models offer reproducibility and control for evaluating antimicrobial performance, they fail to capture the biological complexity of polymicrobial infections commonly encountered in clinical settings. In reality, implant-associated infections are often caused by diverse microbial communities, including anaerobic bacteria, fungi, and antibiotic-resistant strains, which can interact synergistically to enhance biofilm stability, pathogenicity, and resistance to host immune responses [213]. This complexity significantly influences microbial adhesion, biofilm maturation [213], and ultimately the efficacy of antimicrobial coatings. Therefore, while single-species models serve as valuable tools for preliminary evaluation, there is a critical need for more clinically relevant infection models that incorporate polymicrobial biofilms. Without such models, the translational potential and real-world effectiveness of hydrogel-based antibacterial strategies may be overestimated.

Figure 5. Anti-infection hydrogel coatings. A) Representative fluorescence images (scale bar= 20 μm) of *S. aureus* and *E. coli* bacteria strains on control Ti and hydrogel coated substrates with chitosan hydrogel cross-linked with either genipin (Ti-CHIGP) or polyethylene glycol (Ti-CHIPEG), showing bacteria adhesion and viability. Reproduced with permission from [200]. Copyright 2023, Elsevier. B) Percentage *E. coli* area-coverage for pristine and hydrogel-coated surfaces under static and flow incubation conditions. Reproduced with permission from [164]. Copyright 2020, Wiley. C) Quantification of live *S. mutans* adhesion on bare AW, PEG-coated AW (PEG), and CS/PEG-coated AW surfaces, based on fluorescence microscopy analysis [179], and D) Quantitative evaluations of *S. mutans* bacterial colonies on the same specimens. Reproduced with permission from [179]. Copyright 2020, ACS E) Schematic illustration of a dental appliance design featuring dual anti-infective functions, showing that PEGylation reduces bacterial adhesion via a surface hydration layer, while the addition of chitosan imparts antibacterial activity to further suppress microbial colonization. Reproduced with permission from [179]. Copyright 2020 ACS. F) Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images (scale bar= 100 μm) of various pathogens in contact with DMDC-Q-g-EM hydrogel and control. Reproduced with permission from [167]. Copyright 2010, Springer Nature. Schematic illustration (G) and computer simulation (H) of the bacteria killing mechanism of DMDC-Q-g-EM hydrogel via an anion sponge' model, in which the negatively charged bacterial membrane is 'suctioned' into the pores of the hydrogel coating and disturbed. Reproduced with permission from [167]. Copyright 2010, Springer Nature.

Table 1: A summary of studies on anti-infection hydrogel coatings, including their immobilization approaches, stability, and in vitro/in vivo evaluations.

Hydrogel coating	Substrate/s	Immobilization approach	Stability evaluations and results	In vitro results	In vivo results	References
Chitosan/alkynyl chitosan	SS wires	Electrodeposition	N/A	The chitosan/alkynyl chitosan hydrogel coating showed higher effectiveness in preventing the growth of <i>E. coli</i> and <i>S. aureus</i> compared to chitosan hydrogel, as demonstrated by the inhibition zone assays	N/A	[141]
Chitosan	Ti implants	SIP and grafting using either genipin or PEG as crosslinkers	Hydrolytic and enzymatic degradation assays (in the absence and presence of lysozyme) showed that the genipin-crosslinked hydrogel coating exhibits a lower degradation rate than the PEG-crosslinked counterpart	The hydrogel-coated Ti disks showed improved cytocompatibility (with human lung fibroblasts) and reduced haemolytic activity. They also showed significantly reduced <i>E. coli</i> biofilm formation, strong contact-killing antibacterial activity against both strains of <i>E. coli</i> and <i>S. aureus</i>	A 13-week subcutaneous implantation of hydrogel-coated implants showed no adverse effects and minimal tissue response, compared to the control	[200]
Polyacrylamide	PVC and Si tubes	SIP and grafting using DMAA as monomers	Under continuous shear in a rheometer, the hydrogel-coated tubes exhibited a significantly lower coefficient of friction compared to uncoated tubes, indicating enhanced mechanical robustness. Additionally, the hydrogel coating withstood continuous	In vitro bacterial adhesion and colonization of <i>E. coli</i> were significantly reduced on the hydrogel-coated tubes, incubated in the bacteria media, under both static and flow conditions	The hydrogel-coated tube showed a significant increase in occlusion time, when implanted as an arterial bypass on the iliac artery of Bama pigs	[164]

			saline flow at physiologically relevant rates (~1.5 L/min) and pressures (~100 mmHg) without notable changes in water contact angle or coating thickness			
Polyacrylamide loaded with ZnO NPs	Glass coverslips	Silanization and SIP	N/A	The ZnO NPs-loaded hydrogel coatings demonstrated strong antimicrobial activity against E. coli, with bactericidal effects starting at 10 wt.% ZnO for thin films (1 μm) and 5 wt.% for thick films (4 μm). CFU counts and visual analysis confirmed a ZnO concentration-dependent reduction in bacterial growth, establishing a minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of 0.74–1.25 μg/cm ²	N/A	[165]
Epsilon-poly-l-lysine-graft-methacrylamide	Plastic disks	Plasma treatment and grafting	N/A	The hydrogel-coated disks exhibited antimicrobial activity, evidenced by a logarithmic reduction in viable bacterial and fungal counts	N/A	[169]
Poly (ethylene-glycol diacrylate)-acrylic acid (PEGDA-AA) loaded with CIP	Ti sheets	Electrosynthesis	N/A	The CIP-loaded hydrogel coatings on Ti demonstrated strong antibacterial activity against MRSA, as evidenced by significant inhibition zones in agar diffusion assays, with zone sizes directly correlating with the amount of CIP released, confirming sustained drug	N/A	[145]

				delivery and effective antibacterial function		
PEG and chitosan	SS wire/sheets and Si wafers	Silanization and SIP	The hydrogel coating maintained long-lasting antimicrobial activity over 7 days	In vitro adhesion and colony formation assays using bacterial cultures on the hydrogel-coated substrates demonstrated a 98.8% reduction in bacterial adhesion after 5 hours and a 93.3% suppression of colony formation over 7 days, confirming their short-term antifouling and long-term antimicrobial effectiveness	N/A	[179]

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4. INJECTABLE HYDROGELS TO CONTROL INFECTIONS

Building upon the integration of hydrogels into increasingly sophisticated platforms such as microfluidic implantable devices, injectable hydrogels have garnered recognition as a promising strategy towards the development of multifunctional biomaterials. While hydrogel-based microdevices enable precise control over diagnostics and therapeutic release, injectable systems offer distinct advantages in clinical scenarios that demand minimally invasive application, geometric adaptability, and localized therapeutic delivery[214]. These properties are particularly beneficial in the effective management of microbial infections [61]. Such infections include conditions like osteomyelitis, septic arthritis, surgical site infections, and periodontal or peri-implant diseases, which are frequently associated with biofilm-forming pathogens. By adhering to biomaterials or damaged tissues, these pathogens develop protective extracellular matrices that confer resistance to conventional antimicrobial therapies[215]. The chronic nature of these infections frequently results in tissue degradation and irregular defects that require not only antimicrobial intervention but also structural and functional restoration.

In this context, the versatility of hydrogels has positioned them as valuable systems for localized infection control and tissue regeneration, particularly in anatomically complex or infection-compromised sites [215-217]. Their formulation enables administration in a liquid or semi-solid form, followed by in situ gelation, allowing for conformal filling of irregular defects and prolonged retention at the target site. Through strategic modification of their composition and network architecture, these systems enable the encapsulation of antimicrobial agents and their controlled delivery, achieving high local drug concentrations with minimal systemic toxicity [218, 219]. In this context, the performance of injectable hydrogels is strongly influenced by formulation parameters, including polymer composition, concentration, crosslinking density, and the incorporation of responsive or bioactive components. These variables determine key properties including injectability, gelation kinetics, mechanical stability, degradation rate, gelation upon stimulation from intrinsic or extrinsic factors, and compatibility with the host tissue. Tailoring these features is crucial for optimizing hydrogel performance in infection-prone environments, thereby insuring effective therapeutic outcomes.

4.1. Material platforms and synthesis strategies

The functionality of injectable hydrogels strongly relies on the characteristics of the polymer and the selected strategy for network formation [220]. These design parameters not only affect injectability and gelation kinetics but also play a key contribution to the hydrogel's mechanical strength, biodegradation, biocompatibility, and the ability to sustain therapeutic delivery. In infected or inflamed environments—often characterized by anatomical complexity—hydrogel properties must be carefully optimized to balance antimicrobial efficacy with tissue compatibility [216, 221]. In this context, the polymer selection process is fundamental to tailoring the physicochemical and biological characteristics of the hydrogel. Natural polymers including chitosan [221], alginate [222, 223], gelatin[224, 225], and hyaluronic acid [226, 227] being

commonly utilized owing to its inherent biocompatibility, injectability, and in some cases, antimicrobial or regenerative bioactivity [228]. Chitosan, in particular, is a biodegradable cationic polysaccharide known for its tunable physical properties and notable inherent antimicrobial activity [229]. It forms shear-thinning solutions under acidic conditions; however, its limited mechanical strength often necessitates reinforcement with additional materials [221, 229]. Unlike natural polymers, synthetic alternatives such as PEG and PNIPAM facilitate accurate modulation of degradation kinetics, stiffness, and chemical functionality [230, 231]. PEG-based hydrogels are easily functionalized with antimicrobial agents or peptides and can be crosslinked through light- or chemically-activated methods [232]. PNIPAM is a temperature-sensitive polymer that forms a gel at physiological temperatures, making it suitable for minimally invasive delivery applications. However, like many synthetic polymers, it exhibits suboptimal biodegradability and lacks intrinsic bioactive cues unless chemically functionalized [218, 233].

Semisynthetic hydrogels have been developed to combine bioactivity with mechanical and structural precision to overcome the shortcomings associated with both natural and synthetic materials. A widely studied example is GelMA, which is synthesized by methacrylation of gelatin. This modification enables photocrosslinking under mild conditions while preserving a porous, ECM-like structure that supports cell adhesion and proliferation [225]. However, GelMA injectability and mechanical strength exhibit an inverse relationship related to the polymer concentration, necessitating optimization or reinforcement using nanoparticles or nanogels [224]. Similarly, hyaluronic acid methacrylate (HAMA) retains the favorable biological profile of native hyaluronic acid while enabling tunable degradation and network control via photopolymerization [234]. Though, as hyaluronic acid lacks inherent antimicrobial properties, HAMA-based systems can be modified with antimicrobial compounds or nanomaterials to improve their efficacy in the treatment of infections [235]. Overall, functionalization strategies—such as the incorporation of cross-linkable groups [224, 235], antimicrobial moieties [236], or responsive elements [237, 238]—expand the utility of these hydrogels for infection-responsive, on-demand therapeutic delivery.

Crosslinking methods are also crucial for hydrogel performance, particularly in infection-prone environments [239]. Host–guest systems, particularly cyclodextrins or cucurbiturils, enable reversible, non-toxic gelation and controlled drug release under aqueous conditions [216, 218, 240]. Despite their advantages, physically crosslinked hydrogels often exhibit limited mechanical robustness and can degrade rapidly under enzymatic or inflammatory stress. To address these challenges, chemical crosslinking strategies are employed to create more durable and stable networks, making them suitable for demanding conditions such as infection. GelMA-LAP systems, in particular, have been applied in dentistry for *in situ* root canal and periodontal defect filling, supporting antimicrobial delivery and pulp–dentin regeneration [241]. Hydrogel crosslinking facilitated by enzymes such as transglutaminase, tyrosinase, and horseradish peroxidase enables cytocompatible formulations with controllable gelation rates and degradation behavior, modulated

by the concentration of the enzyme [242]. Altogether, these material choices and synthesis strategies facilitate the design of injectable hydrogels that integrate targeted delivery, stimuli-responsiveness, mechanical robustness, and infection-specific functionality.

4.2. Design considerations for injectable antimicrobial hydrogels

4.2.1. Antimicrobial mechanisms and agent incorporation

The antimicrobial efficacy of injectable hydrogels is primarily determined by their inherent antimicrobial activity and capacity to deliver therapeutic agents locally. These systems can be broadly categorized into (i) hydrogels with inherent antimicrobial activity, and (ii) those incorporating antimicrobial substances [218]. Both strategies aim to address the limitations of systemic antibiotic therapy—such as inadequate penetration in infected tissues, rapid clearance, and the risk of resistance development—by enabling localized, sustained, and targeted treatment.

Inherent antimicrobial hydrogels are typically based on cationic or amphiphilic polymers capable of disrupting bacterial membranes. For instance, chitosan exerts intrinsic antibacterial potential due to its high density of protonated amino moieties that engage in ionic interactions with the anionic components of bacterial cell walls [229]. The antimicrobial efficacy of chitosan can be further enhanced through quaternization—for example, by converting it to hydroxypropyltrimethyl ammonium chloride chitosan (HACC), a derivative that enhances chitosan's aqueous solubility and strengthens its electrostatic interactions with bacterial membranes [221, 229]. Through Schiff base chemistry, Deng et al. [243] synthesized a biocompatible, injectable, and self-repairing hydrogel by combining HACC with DABC. The system effectively inhibited both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, including *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, along with desirable properties for wound healing including an ECM-mimicking architecture, biocompatibility, adequate compressive strength, and excellent water retention. Importantly, the enhanced in vitro antimicrobial efficacy was attributed to the integrated action of quaternary ammonium moieties and amino groups on the chitosan backbone, which disrupt bacterial membranes, alongside Schiff base linkages, which themselves may exert antibacterial effects. These findings were supported by SEM imaging, which showed substantial bacterial deformation and lysis after 24 hours of hydrogel exposure [243].

In another study, Xin et al., [244] introduced SNP@PCN@Gel, a multifunctional hybrid hydrogel that is injectable and responsive to light stimulation to combat bacterial infections and promote wound healing via synergistic photothermal, photodynamic, chemodynamic, gas, and ion therapies. SEM revealed extensive morphological damage to *E. coli* and *S. aureus* with disrupted membranes and cell collapse, particularly under light irradiation. In vivo studies in bacteria-infected mouse wound models demonstrated that the hydrogels effectively reduced bacterial load and significantly improved healing outcomes, including accelerated wound closure, epithelial regeneration, collagen matrix formation, and new blood vessel development, without inducing systemic toxicity. Similarly, a polymeric hydrogel constructed using carboxymethyl chitosan

(CMCS) and PEI demonstrated strong intrinsic antimicrobial activity without the incorporation of antibiotics[245]. Formed through hydrogen bonding interactions, the CMCS/PEI hydrogel exhibited injectability, biocompatibility, and notable antibacterial efficacy, with in vitro assays showing the number of *S. aureus* and *E. coli* CFUs decreased proportionally with increasing concentration. The antimicrobial effect was mainly linked to the cationic nature of PEI, which destabilizes bacterial membranes, while CMCS contributes solubility and wound-healing support. In vivo, the optimized 5:5 formulation achieved nearly complete wound healing by 14 days, reinforcing its potential for infection control and tissue repair[245].

In parallel, many hydrogels are engineered to serve as localized drug-delivery platforms for antibacterial agents such as antibiotics[219, 246], metal ions[247, 248], antimicrobial peptides (AMPs), and photoactivatable compounds[227, 249]. These hydrogels form in situ and provide a 3D porous matrix that enables the localized and sustained delivery of therapeutic compounds at the infection site, thereby offering several clinical advantages. These include enhancing localized drug accumulation, with reduced systemic involvement, and minimizing the risk of antimicrobial resistance [218]. Among these, antibiotic-loaded systems remain the most widely investigated and utilized [218]. As an example, a study recently introduced a 3D-printed GelMA hydrogel integrated with PLGA nanoparticles, designed for the dual delivery of rifampicin and vancomycin—two antibiotics commonly used to treat *S. aureus*-associated implant infections [250]. The GelMA-PLGA formulation enabled sustained and localized antibiotic release for up to 21 days, effectively eradicating wild-type *S. aureus* strains as well as rifampicin- and vancomycin-resistant variants. Notably, the dual-drug delivery platform prevented the emergence of resistance observed in single-antibiotic systems, highlighting its potential in preventing biofilm-associated implant infections [250].

Beyond GelMA, other matrix platforms have demonstrated high potential for different infection treatment targets. A notable use of injectable hydrogels in Dentistry involves the management of periodontitis, a persistent inflammatory condition associated with alveolar bone degradation. For instance, to address both infection-induced inflammation and the need for tissue regeneration, a thermoresponsive hydrogel system based on chitosan (CS), β -GP, and gelatin components was developed to co-deliver aspirin and erythropoietin (EPO) (**Figure 6A**)[251]. This injectable system forms a gel at body temperature within 5 min and supports sustained drug release over 21 days. Aspirin is rapidly released during the early phase to suppress the inflammatory microenvironment by inhibiting COX-2 and MMP-9 expression. In contrast, EPO is gradually released to promote angiogenesis and alveolar bone regeneration, potentially through pathways such as ephrinB2–EphB4 signalling. In vivo studies demonstrated significant reduction in inflammatory markers osteoclast activity, and complete recovery of alveolar bone height and periodontal tissue structure (**Figure 6B and C**) [251].

Figure 6. A) Schematic of the thermosensitive CS/ β -GP/gelatin hydrogel loaded with aspirin and erythropoietin (EPO), designed for in situ gelation and dual-phase drug release. B) Top - In vivo gel formation and biocompatibility with subcutaneous injection of PBS or pre-gels in nude mice; dotted circles show hydrogel formation after 5 min. Bottom - Skin removed after 2 weeks to reveal remaining hydrogels. C) Micro-CT analysis of alveolar bone regeneration in a ligature-induced periodontitis rat model, with CEJ-ABC distance used to quantify bone loss. Reproduced with permission [251]. Copyright 2019, Elsevier.

Beyond systems that incorporate antibiotics and anti-inflammatory drugs directly into the hydrogel matrix, increasing attention has been directed toward addressing primary limitations of injectable hydrogels as drug delivery vehicles: their propensity for burst release, particularly with water-soluble agents. While hydrogels are widely recognized as excellent drug carriers owing to their ability to retain water, compatibility with biological tissues, and customizable pore structure, allowing for prolonged and targeted delivery of certain compounds remains a significant challenge [218]. This is especially true for small, hydrophilic drugs like metronidazole (MTZ), an antibiotic commonly used for anaerobic infections. Due to its moderate water solubility, MTZ tends to diffuse rapidly out of hydrogels, particularly in oral environments where salivary flow can quickly dilute the therapeutic dose. Researchers have explored strategies such as polymer-drug conjugation, drug crystallization, and encapsulation into hydrophobic or physically confining microdomains to slow down diffusion kinetics [218]. Among these, microencapsulation stands out as a versatile and effective approach for controlling the release of MTZ. Recent studies introduced MTZ-loaded chitosan microcapsules (CS@MTZ), which not only enable controlled drug release but also function as a crosslinking component within the hydrogel network [252]. These microcapsules were incorporated into a PVA hydrogel crosslinked with 4-carboxyphenylboronic acid (CPBA), forming an injectable hydrogel (PVA@CS@MTZ) that demonstrates strong underwater adhesion, excellent injectability, and antibacterial efficacy against anaerobic pathogens [252].

Beyond the incorporation of conventional antibiotics, injectable hydrogels have also been developed to deliver metal-based antimicrobial agents [247, 248, 253], which offer complementary or alternative mechanisms of action—particularly valuable in the context of increasing antibiotic resistance. Silver (Ag^+) is the most extensively studied metal-based antimicrobial agents [218]. Zhao et al. [247] developed an injectable, self-healing hydrogel (ADCM@Ag) comprising carboxymethyl chitosan and aldehyde-functionalized dextran (ADCM), which enabled in situ green generation of AgNPs through Schiff base crosslinking. This system combines strong antibacterial efficacy (>85% bacterial killing) with favorable injectability, shape adaptability, and cytocompatibility. Similarly, a mussel-inspired injectable GelMA/PVA hydrogel incorporating polyzwitterion-stabilized AgNPs demonstrated enhanced antibacterial activity and improved hemocompatibility [248]. Moreover, targeting diabetic wounds, an in situ photo-cross-linkable hydrogel embedded with heterojunction Ag@ZnO nanoparticles achieved synergistic antimicrobial action through dual release of Ag^+ and Zn^{2+} and reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation [254]. Mechanistically, ROS damage bacteria by inducing oxidative stress, which disrupts cellular components such as membranes, proteins, and DNA. They interact with phospholipids, causing lipid peroxidation, and oxidize proteins, leading to structural and functional impairment. Additionally, ROS can fragment nucleic acids, ultimately triggering cell death through irreversible oxidative damage [254]. Across these platforms, the integration of nanoparticles facilitated controlled and sustained antimicrobial activity while minimizing cytotoxicity, underscoring their potential in the management of infected or chronic wounds.

Building on diverse strategies for delivering antimicrobial substances—including antimicrobials, anti-inflammatories, and metal-based nanoparticles—the next frontier in injectable hydrogel design centers on modulating drug delivery based on infection-associated signals. Unlike conventional systems driven by passive diffusion or fixed degradation, stimuli-responsive hydrogels enable on-site therapeutic release governed by stimuli like pH shifts, redox state, bacterial enzymes, or light [238]. This approach reduces premature drug loss, prolongs therapeutic efficacy, and enhances precision in targeting microbial activity, particularly in biofilm-infected or necrotic tissues. The following section discusses how these systems are engineered to exploit infection-associated microenvironments for controlled release and therapeutic activation.

4.2.2. Stimuli-responsive behaviour for antimicrobial action

The stimuli-responsive behaviour is a cornerstone in the design of injectable antimicrobial hydrogels, facilitating targeted drug delivery triggered by specific biochemical or physical cues associated with infection. These systems can react to endogenous stimuli, such as acidic pH, elevated ROS, or bacterial enzyme activity, or by external stimuli, such as light, temperature, or magnetic fields [238]. Hydrogels responsive to pH can degrade or swell in acidic microenvironments, which are characteristic of infected and inflamed tissues [238]. Similarly, ROS-responsive hydrogels can trigger the release of antimicrobial agents in environments with elevated oxidative stress, a condition frequently observed in infection sites due to immune cell activity [238].

Among the various stimulus-responsive hydrogels, those responsive to pH and ROS have demonstrated considerable potential for infection-associated bone regeneration. Inflammatory conditions and bacterial activity commonly lead to a localized decrease in pH and an excessive accumulation of ROS, both of which are detrimental to osteoblast function and contribute to delayed bone healing. To address these challenges, Qi et al., [237] engineered a smart GelMA-based hydrogel using boronate complexes for the dual delivery of proanthocyanidin—an antioxidant with osteoinductive properties—and amikacin, a broad-spectrum antibiotic. The boronate complexes are cleaved in response to acidic pH and elevated ROS, enabling on-demand therapeutics release within the inflammatory microenvironment. The hydrogel's porous structure, mechanical strength, and biodegradability support tissue regeneration, while its injectability allows for minimally invasive and defect-specific application [237].

Other ROS-based strategies focus not on scavenging but also on generating ROS to achieve potent, broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity, most notably through light-triggered photodynamic approaches [227, 255, 256]. In this context, photoresponsive injectable hydrogels are capable of localized and on-demand activation of ROS under external light stimuli, enabling spatial control over antibacterial action with minimal systemic toxicity [257]. These photodynamic hydrogels embed photosensitizers (e.g., black phosphorus, Yb₂O₃, MoS₂) that generate bactericidal ROS

upon light activation, enabling effective infection treatment even in complex or irregular tissue sites [218, 257]. An injectable hydrogel incorporating MnO₂ nanosheets loaded with a photosensitizer and CaO₂ nanoparticles within a calcium-crosslinked alginate matrix was developed as a nanozyme-reinforced system [255]. CaO₂ generates H₂O₂, which MnO₂ converts to O₂, alleviating hypoxia and enhancing ROS production during photodynamic therapy. This light-activated hydrogel achieved over 99% elimination of *S. aureus* and *E. coli* and significantly reduced biofilm biomass under hypoxic conditions [215]. Using a *S. aureus* biofilm-infected wound model, the hydrogel combined with light significantly reduced bacterial load, promoted wound closure, enhanced skin regeneration and collagen deposition, and lowered IL-6 and TNF- α levels. However, ROS-based PDT requires high ROS levels for efficacy, posing a risk of oxidative damage to healthy tissue.

Combining PDT with mild PTT offers a promising approach aimed at boosting antimicrobial performance while reducing adverse effects. Zhang et al. [227] developed a photo-initiated, dual-crosslinked injectable hydrogel (HA-DA/Fe³⁺/PCN@BP) composed of dopamine-functionalized hyaluronic acid and black phosphorus/PCN-224 nanosheets (**Figure 7A**). Coordination with Fe³⁺ formed a self-healing, injectable network. Upon 660 nm irradiation, PCN@BP generated ROS that triggered dopamine oxidation, forming covalent pDA crosslinks, reinforcing the hydrogel. Dopamine-derived catechol groups enabled strong adhesion even in moist or irregular tissues. The photo-responsive system allowed tunable stiffness and synergistic ROS/PTT effects, effectively eradicating bacteria. Fluorescence and SEM imaging showed significant membrane damage in *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, especially under combined PDT–PTT. In vitro, the hydrogel showed dose-dependent fibroblast proliferation and enhanced migration (**Figure 7B**). In vivo, it significantly reduced bacterial load, promoted reepithelialization, and improved granulation tissue formation in infected wound models, highlighting its therapeutic potential.

Figure 7. Overview of the antimicrobial performance of photoresponsive and thermoresponsive injectable hydrogels. (A–B) The HA-DA/Fe³⁺/PCN@BP hydrogel features a dynamic physically and chemically double-crosslinked injectable network, offering tunable mechanical properties and synergistic PTT/PDT antibacterial activity that enhances wound healing under laser irradiation (A). Antimicrobial efficacy is evidenced by live/dead staining, which shows increased red fluorescence (dead *S. aureus*) post-treatment, while SEM images reveal extensive bacterial membrane disruption in the PTDT group, with red arrows highlighting ruptured surfaces (B). Reproduced with permission.[227] Copyright 2022, Wiley. (C–E) Similarly, the CS/Nal-P-113/PDNPs hydrogel was engineered to combat oxidative stress, inflammation, and bacterial infection associated with periodontitis (C). Its thermosensitive nature allows it to transition from a liquid at room temperature to a gel at 37 °C, facilitating minimally invasive application (D). The hydrogel’s antibacterial effect is further validated by CFU assays, which show substantial reductions in bacterial colony counts following treatment (E). Reproduced with permission.[258] Copyright 2022, Elsevier.

Thermosensitive injectable hydrogels feature temperature-triggered sol-gel transition at physiological conditions, allowing in situ gel formation, enabling precise filling of irregular wounds, and prolonging localized retention [238]. For example, a hydrogel composed of Poloxamer 407, lysine, and 3,4-dihydroxyphenylacetic acid (DOPAC) exhibited injectability, rapid gelation at 33 °C, and strong antibacterial and antioxidant properties, achieving 99.77% wound closure by day 14 in a skin defect model. To address the challenge of accessing endodontic root canals, Reis-Prado et al. [246] designed a thermoresponsive hydrogel system derived from chitosan with 3% azithromycin. The hydrogel demonstrated effective action against *E. faecalis* biofilms, cytocompatibility as well as and enhanced vascularization and tissue regeneration in a

rat periapical disease model. Similarly, a recently reported chitosan-based hydrogel incorporating antimicrobial peptides (Nal-P-113) and PDA nanoparticles (PDNPs) achieved both antibacterial and antioxidant effects (**Figure 7C**) [258]. The hydrogel exhibited thermogelling at 37 °C (**Figure 7D**), ~80% ROS-scavenging activity, and ~99% antibacterial efficacy against *S. gordonii*, *F. nucleatum*, and *P. gingivalis* (**Figure 7E**), highlighting its potential for localized periodontitis treatment.

In addition to thermal, pH, and ROS-responsive systems, enzyme- and electrically responsive hydrogels are gaining attention as effective biomaterials for localized therapy. Enzyme-sensitive hydrogels have been developed with the purpose of degrade or release their cargo, enabling site-specific activation in infected or inflamed tissues [259]. Electroresponsive hydrogels, on the other hand, incorporate conductive polymers such as polypyrrole or PEDOT, allowing for externally controlled drug release under applied voltage [238]. Importantly, combining multiple stimuli can enhance precision and therapeutic control. For instance, a dual-responsive antibacterial injectable hydrogel was developed based on conductive copolymer polyaniline and oxidized dextran (OD), enabling both voltage- and pH-triggered release of amoxicillin [260]. This system demonstrated an “on-off” pulse release mechanism under electric stimulation and pH-responsive behavior, following a Fickian diffusion model. With tunable gelation time, degradation rate, and electroconductivity (up to 0.079 S/m), alongside inherent antibacterial activity and excellent biocompatibility, such dual-responsive hydrogels represent advanced drug delivery systems for tailored treatment of chronic infections [260].

Overall, the design of responsive hydrogels requires a precise equilibrium between responsiveness and mechanical integrity. Premature breakdown or uncontrolled release can compromise efficacy and safety, while insufficient responsiveness may fail to activate therapeutic action when needed. Therefore, stimuli-responsive design must be tailored to the infection microenvironment, ensuring that the hydrogel remains inactive until triggered by clinically relevant conditions. When executed effectively, this strategy offers a powerful platform for developing next-generation antimicrobial therapies with high specificity, reduced toxicity, and enhanced regenerative outcomes.

4.2.3. Functional injectability and in-situ performance

A key requirement for injectable antimicrobial hydrogels is their functional performance at the target site. This involves easy and site-specific delivery (injectability), rapid and stable gelation after administration, mechanical properties tailored to the local tissue, and strong tissue adhesiveness to ensure retention at the application site. Their injectability is primarily determined by their viscosity, flow characteristics under shear, and gelation timing are critical aspects that need to be meticulously tuned to have smooth extrusion through a syringe while avoiding premature gelation [230]. Shear-thinning properties allow the hydrogel to respond to applied forces by flowing during injection and recover its structure upon reaching the target site, while controlled sol-gel transitions enable in situ solidification, providing mechanical integrity and retention within

the defect [216, 231]. The rheological profile (e.g., storage modulus, loss modulus, and viscosity over shear rate) is critical for defining usability, with viscoelasticity characterized by a storage modulus (G') exceeding the loss modulus (G''). These parameters are typically measured through frequency and strain sweep tests to establish the linear viscoelastic region and quantify the stiffness and resistance to deformation [216, 231]. Standard protocols typically include assessing viscosity as influenced by shear rate changes to confirm thinning behavior, as well as evaluating gelation kinetics using either the inverted vial test or rheometry under physiological conditions (e.g., 37 °C) [216, 230, 231, 261].

Syringeability and injectability are assessed via measurement of the required pressure to push the hydrogel through a syringe barrel—commonly using 18–27 gauge needles—at a constant rate, with acceptable formulations requiring less than 30 N of injection force and ensuring high expulsion efficiency [216, 262]. Overall, factors including polymer content, chain length, crosslinking density, and temperature sensitivity play a critical role in tuning gelation properties [216]. For instance, higher polymer concentrations can enhance mechanical strength but may compromise injectability due to increased viscosity, while low concentrations may result in weak or unstable gels [230]. Filimonova et al. [263] found that higher polymer concentrations promoted rapid gel formation and reinforced structural integrity, but also caused more pronounced shrinkage throughout the processing stage. Gelation must occur within a clinically relevant timeframe post-injection to avoid burst release, typically triggered by thermal, pH, enzymatic, or chemical stimuli. Delivery conditions also affect hydrogel architecture. For example, Hernandez et al. [261] showed that high extrusion speeds or poor shear-thinning behavior can disrupt microstructure, leading to reduced retention or therapeutic efficacy. Their flow model emphasized the need for accurate high-shear rheological data to ensure predictable performance across varying flow conditions and needle sizes. Mechanical properties such as tensile strength, compressive modulus, and elasticity are critical for ensuring that the hydrogel can withstand physiological stresses without mechanical failure. These parameters are commonly evaluated via compression tests and oscillatory rheology to assess the hydrogel's ability to maintain structural integrity, resist deformation, and match the mechanical environment of the surrounding tissue. This is especially important in dynamic biological settings, such as wound sites or implant environment, where inadequate mechanical performance can lead to early degradation, poor tissue integration, or treatment failure [61].

Injectable hydrogels often suffer from intrinsic softness and instability, limiting their mechanical performance. Various nanoparticles—such as silica, graphene oxide, carbon nanotubes, nanoclays, and nanocellulose—have been incorporated into polymeric matrices to reinforce the network and enhance bioactivity, drug delivery, or hemostatic functions [264]. For example, incorporating rigid CNCs into hydrazone-crosslinked networks increased storage modulus up to 35-fold, improved gelation kinetics, reduced swelling, and maintained cell viability [265]. Gantar et al. [266] showed that adding bioactive glass nanoparticles to Au-(PEGSH)₄ hydrogels significantly boosted

mechanical strength by restricting polymer chain mobility, while preserving self-healing. Similarly, Shi et al. [267] demonstrated that MgSiO₃ nanoparticles in bisphosphonate-functionalized hyaluronic acid hydrogels enhanced storage modulus and shear resistance through reversible coordination bonds between Mg²⁺ ions and polymer chains. Rheological studies further emphasize that optimal mechanical stability depends on controlled polymer mixing—both insufficient and excessive mixing can compromise network integrity [268].

Self-healing ability, tissue adhesion, and high porosity are critical features that support the functional performance of injectable hydrogels by promoting mechanical resilience and biological integration [218, 268]. Adhesion is essential for infection-prone and wound-healing applications and can be markedly enhanced in hydrogels through strategic material design [218]. As reviewed by Mondal et al. [220], effective approaches under moist or dynamic physiological conditions involve incorporating reactive groups—such as aldehydes [269], amines [270], and catechols [271]—to form covalent and non-covalent bonds with tissue surfaces. In addition, catechol groups, inspired by mussel foot proteins, offer strong wet adhesion, while dynamic reversible crosslinking mechanisms such as Schiff base [226] and hydrazone bonds [272] contribute to both cohesive strength and self-healing capabilities [214]. Thus, fine-tuning the crosslinking density and polymer chain architecture—such as the molecular weight between crosslinks—allows control over porosity, swelling, and mechanical robustness. Tavafoghi et al. [222] developed a hybrid injectable hydrogel designed to enhance toughness through ion-induced reversible crosslinking. Combining GelMA with methacrylate-modified alginate (AlgMA) and incorporating divalent cations with photocrosslinkable bonds produced an injectable bioadhesive hydrogel with over 600% greater toughness than GelMA alone, highlighting its promise as a durable and cost-effective tissue sealant.

4.2.4. Biodegradation, biocompatibility, and host interaction

The success of antimicrobial injectable hydrogels in biomedical applications depends on a delicate balance between biodegradability, biocompatibility, and favourable host interaction. The degradation rate must be finely tuned to align with the specific application, whether rapid for acute infections or slower for long-term regeneration, while ensuring that degradation byproducts are non-toxic and non-inflammatory [214, 218]. Additionally, hydrogel degradation plays a vital role in tissue regeneration by progressively clearing space for new tissue to grow and integrate, facilitating natural remodelling and functional recovery [214]. The composition of the hydrogel and its implantation environment (e.g., oral cavity, joints, bone defects) influence the degradation profile, which can be modulated using hydrolytic, enzymatic, thiol-exchange, or photolytic mechanisms. Importantly, natural polymers like hyaluronic acid, chitosan, and alginate degrade more rapidly and can be stabilized by crosslinking to prevent premature breakdown, while synthetic polymers often require structural modification or blending to enable appropriate resorption [214, 218]. For example, redox-responsive disulfide-crosslinked PEG hydrogels have been engineered to allow precise modulation of degradation kinetics [273]. In vitro, degradation

times ranged from 2 to 32 days, depending on polymer concentration: 3% hydrogels degraded within 2 days, whereas 10–15% formulations remained stable for up to 32 days. This degradation rate directly influenced the release kinetics of encapsulated proteins. Integration of recombinant human bone morphogenetic protein-2 (rhBMP-2) enabled sustained release during hydrogel degradation, correlating with enhanced ectopic bone formation in vivo [273].

Hydrogels are generally considered highly biocompatible, particularly when composed of natural polymers or hybrid formulations combining synthetic polymers with biomolecules [274]. These combinations can enhance drug release control, improve mechanical stability, and mitigate inflammatory responses. For example, Wang et al. [275] engineered an injectable hydrogel, SrmE20, to direct macrophage polarization through a sequential transition from M0 to M1 to M2 phenotypes, thereby promoting antibacterial activity and tissue regeneration (**Figure 8A**). Initially, ethanol in the formulation promoted M1 polarization and proinflammatory cytokine release (e.g., TNF- α), aiding bacterial clearance. By day 4, its dissipation allowed the hydrogel's cationic and phenolic components to promote M2 polarization, increasing IL-10 and TGF- β 1 while reducing IL-1 β (**Figure 8B**). In infected wounds, this immune modulation accelerated healing via early M2 accumulation, enhanced angiogenesis, and collagen deposition. Immunogenic and antimicrobial hydrogels offer notable therapeutic advantages, particularly against infections, but their design must balance antimicrobial efficacy with biocompatibility [276]. High concentrations of antimicrobial agents within hydrogels can produce reactive byproducts, leading to cytotoxicity and heightened inflammation without proper biological integration [218]. Thus, optimizing composition and release profiles of these agents is essential to minimize adverse effects. Beyond microbial reduction, the intrinsic antimicrobial properties of hydrogels help prevent tissue degradation and modulate immune responses, further enhancing their therapeutic potential.

4.3. Bridging laboratory findings to in vivo infection models

The development of antimicrobial hydrogels for implant-associated infections requires thorough evaluation in both in vitro and in vivo models to ensure safety and efficacy. In vitro systems provide controlled conditions to assess antimicrobial activity, enabling manipulation of variables such as bacterial species, biofilm maturity, and hydrogel composition. However, inconsistencies in antimicrobial concentrations and exposure times across studies hinder comparability and the establishment of standardized protocols. Moreover, these models often oversimplify infection dynamics by focusing on single-species biofilms, failing to capture the polymicrobial complexity of implant-associated infections [218]. While advanced tools like next-generation sequencing [277] offer deeper insights into biofilm communities, their use in in vitro studies remains limited. Furthermore, in vitro models lack representation of host immune responses, tissue interactions, and mechanical stresses found in vivo.

In vivo studies are essential for evaluating antimicrobial hydrogels, as they capture the complexities of living systems, including immune responses, tissue integration, and systemic

effects. Animal models—from rodents to larger mammals—have been used to assess their efficacy in preventing or treating implant-associated infections [218]. However, selecting an appropriate model is critical, as each presents specific advantages and limitations that must align with the intended clinical application and therapeutic goals. For instance, in wound healing studies, rodent models are frequently utilized due to their manageable size, cost-effectiveness, and well-characterized immune systems. In a representative investigation, Wang et al. [275] employed an anti-contraction full-thickness wound model in mice (diameter = 6 mm), infected with *S. aureus*, to assess the regenerative efficacy of the SrmE20 hydrogel (**Figure 8C**). The hydrogel significantly reduced the bacterial burden, accelerated wound closure, and facilitated the restoration of normal skin architecture by day 16. Histological analysis revealed markedly fewer bacteria in tissue sections compared to untreated controls. Another relevant model simulated diabetic wound infections by creating full-thickness *S. aureus*-infected dorsal wounds in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats [278]. The wounds were treated with a composite system comprising functional core layers and a decellularized ECM (dECM) hydrogel, combined with near-infrared (808 nm) irradiation. This dual treatment approach achieved approximately a 6-log reduction in bacterial load, attenuated inflammation, and significantly enhanced vascularization and collagen deposition, as evidenced by histological and immunohistochemical analyses (e.g., CD31 and type I collagen). These examples underscore the importance of tailored *in vivo* models—such as infected full-thickness or diabetic wounds—for evaluating hydrogel degradation, drug release kinetics, anti-biofilm efficacy, and regenerative potential under physiologically relevant conditions. Nevertheless, notable differences in skin structure between rodents and humans may limit the direct translatability of findings.

Other specific applications must also be considered before choosing an appropriate animal infection model, especially in the context of periodontal research. Rodents are frequently used due to their anatomical similarities to human periodontium, ease of handling, and the availability of genetic tools [279]. For example, a rat periodontitis bone defect model was used to assess the regenerative potential of an injectable bioglass hydrogel incorporating quercetin (i-BH-Q system) [280]. This model mimicked the clinical progression of periodontitis through ligature-induced plaque accumulation around the maxillary second molar, which led to localized inflammation, oxidative stress, and alveolar bone resorption (**Figure 8D**). This model replicated the clinical progression of periodontitis by inducing plaque accumulation around the maxillary second molar via ligature placement, resulting in localized inflammation, oxidative stress, and alveolar bone resorption (**Figure 8D**). Following hydrogel injection into the periodontal defects, maxillary specimens were harvested and analyzed using micro-CT (**Figure 8D-F**). The quercetin-loaded hydrogel significantly promoted alveolar bone regeneration, as evidenced by reduced vertical space from the cemento-enamel junction to the alveolar crest compared to untreated periodontitis controls (**Figure 8G**) [281]. However, disparities in immune responses, microbiota composition, and overall physiology between animal models and humans may hinder direct clinical translation.

In addition, ethical concerns, financial costs, and inter-model variability remain significant limitations in preclinical research.

Figure 8. A) Schematic and experimental validation of an injectable hydrogel promoting macrophage polarization (M0→M1→M2) for infection control and tissue regeneration. B) In vitro assays with RAW 264.7 cells assessed phenotypic shifts and cytokine expression. C) Diagram showing the proposed mechanism of wound healing in infected sites with reduced tissue contraction. Reproduced with permission.[275] Copyright 2022, Elsevier. D) In vivo, hydrogel was tested in a rat periodontitis model, with treatment applied to bone defects and healing evaluated via E-G) tissue analysis and micro-CT, including measurement of CEJ–ABC distance and visual comparison of maxillary molars. Reproduced with permission. [280] Copyright 2022, Elsevier.

4.4. Commercial landscape and regulatory consideration

The translation of antimicrobial injectable hydrogels from bench to bedside remains limited, with relatively few commercially available products currently addressing infection-related clinical needs. One notable exception is the Defensive Antibacterial Coating (DAC®) which has gained clinical traction for localized antibiotic delivery in implant-associated infections [276, 282]. However, despite its frequent application in human studies, DAC® is supported by a surprisingly limited body of preclinical and in vitro research. This discrepancy underscores a significant translational gap, wherein regulatory approval and market adoption have advanced ahead of comprehensive experimental validation. More broadly, this case exemplifies a pervasive issue in the commercial landscape—namely, the insufficient alignment between early-stage academic research and subsequent clinical implementation [218].

Approval pathways vary depending on the region (e.g., FDA in the U.S. and EMA in Europe), but typically require extensive data on biocompatibility, sterilization, degradation, mechanical properties, and long-term safety[283]. Injectable hydrogels have been broadly studied for multiple therapeutic uses, such as facial correction, osteoarthritis, soft tissue regeneration, and drug delivery. Although over 28 injectable hydrogel-based products have been approved by regulatory agencies such as the FDA or EMA, only a limited number are specifically indicated for the treatment of infections. A notable exception is the DAC® hydrogel—composed of hyaluronic acid and poly(lactic acid) and incorporated with antibiotics—which is currently undergoing clinical evaluation for the management of prosthesis-related infections (NCT04251377) [284].

Overall, while infection-related hydrogel applications are emerging—such as in wound healing and antibiotic delivery—most approved products still focus on aesthetic, orthopaedic, or regenerative indications. As bioactive and adaptive materials continue to evolve, regulatory agencies face increasing pressure to revise evaluation protocols to address their dynamic interactions with host immunity and responsiveness to specific physiological or pathological cues. In infection-related applications, key challenges include validating antimicrobial efficacy against clinically relevant biofilms, ensuring reproducible drug release kinetics, and confirming the non-toxicity of degradation products. Addressing these issues is essential to close the persistent gap between promising in vitro outcomes and successful clinical translation.

5. HYDROGEL IMPLANTS FOR BONE DEFECTS

Trauma-, infection-, or disease-related bone defects continue to be a key concern, affecting patient outcomes and imposing high socioeconomic costs worldwide [285]. Although bone tissue possesses an intrinsic regenerative capacity, this is often insufficient for large or irregular defects, commonly referred to as critical-sized bone defects, which surpass the natural self-healing threshold and require surgical intervention [286]. Bone reconstruction procedures continue to favour autologous grafting as the gold standard, primarily because of its biocompatibility and osteogenic potential; however, the associated limitations—including limited donor constraints including sourcing limitations, donor site trauma, post-operative pain, and infection susceptibility have accelerated the search for synthetic and biomimetic alternatives [286, 287]. Allografts and xenografts provide alternatives to overcome donor tissue limitations; however, they carry risks such as immunogenic responses and graft failure. In parallel, emerging bone tissue engineering (BTE) strategies aim to develop functional biomaterials that closely mimic the composition and biological functions of native bone [286]. These substitutes must meet stringent requirements: they should physically fill the defect, support osteoconduction, promote osteoinduction and osteogenesis, facilitate vascularization, and ultimately restore the structural and functional integrity of bone tissue [287]. In this context, hydrogels have demonstrated effectiveness not only as scaffolds for cell recruitment and osteogenic differentiation but also as drug delivery systems capable of releasing growth factors (e.g., BMP-2, TGF- β , VEGF) and antimicrobial agents in a controlled and localized manner—features particularly valuable in infected or immunocompromised environments [288].

Beyond their composition (natural or synthetic), the efficacy of hydrogel implants is closely linked to their functional design. Ideal hydrogel scaffolds for bone regeneration must exhibit osteoconductive architectures that support cellular infiltration and matrix deposition, osteoinductive characteristics to stimulate stem cell differentiation into osteoblasts, and angiogenic properties to restore vascular networks that sustain tissue remodelling and mineralization [288, 289]. Advances in fabrication technologies such as 3D bioprinting have enabled accurate control of hydrogel geometry and spatial patterning, opening new avenues for patient-specific implants and multifunctional scaffold designs [224, 290, 291]. Furthermore, the advent of 4D printing has introduced stimuli-responsive materials capable of adapting to physiological conditions post-implantation. This innovation offers promising avenues in bone tissue engineering, particularly through the use of shape-memory polymers and hydrogels that facilitate osteogenesis and enhance tissue integration [81, 292]. Moreover, 4D printing aligns with the goals of personalized and sustainable medicine, enabling patient-specific, eco-friendly implants that actively participate in the healing process by mimicking the dynamic nature of living tissues [81]. Altogether, the success of hydrogel implants for bone defects depends on the strategic design of materials and architectures, where factors like responsiveness, degradation rate, mechanical strength, and biocompatibility must be precisely tailored to synchronize with the dynamic stages of bone healing and integration [238, 289, 293].

5.1. Designing hydrogel based on biological functionality

To offer an in-depth perspective on the role of hydrogels in facilitating bone regeneration, this section categorizes current hydrogel platforms based on their primary biological functions: osteoconduction, osteoinduction, angiogenesis, immunomodulation, and responsiveness to external stimuli. Representative materials, functional mechanisms, and in vitro and preclinical outcomes are highlighted.

5.1.1. Hydrogels with osteoconductivity

Osteoconductivity refers to the material's ability to promote new bone growth on its surface, which is influenced by both the biological environment and the interaction with host cells. To enhance this property, bone tissue engineering (BTE) hydrogels often incorporate inorganic components like calcium phosphate ceramics and bioactive glass, as well as cell-loaded biomimetic structures [288, 293]. These additions contribute to essential mechanical integrity and bioactivity, promoting integration with host bone and supporting regeneration, even under load-bearing conditions [294].

Calcium phosphate-based bioceramics are widely used in bone tissue engineering (BTE) due to their compositional resemblance to the mineral phase of bone, excellent osteoconductivity, and biodegradability. However, their application in clinical settings is limited by inadequate mechanical properties and insufficient osteoinductive capacity [289]. Consequently, hydrogel-based systems have been reinforced with bioceramics to support enhanced osteogenesis. For instance, Qiu et al. [295] developed an injectable, photocurable hydrogel based on methacrylated carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC-MA) and spherical HAp, mimicking native bone matrix and conforming to irregular defects. HAp enhanced osteogenesis by providing bioactive adhesion sites that activated integrin-mediated BMP-2/Smad signaling, promoting cell proliferation, osteogenic gene expression, and bone regeneration in a rat cranial defect model. Despite the advantages of HAp incorporation, the composition and behavior of the hydrogel matrix remain critical for optimal performance [295]. In another study, Morais et al. [258] investigated alginate-based hydrogels—alone or combined with chitosan or hyaluronate—as carriers for GR-HAp, demonstrating that hydrogel composition significantly influences physicochemical properties. The Alg/HA hydrogel exhibited the highest degradation rate, favorable swelling, and low extrusion force, supporting its potential for minimally invasive delivery. The study also showed that higher polymer concentrations and stronger ionic crosslinking enhance viscosity and structural integrity, improving bioceramic retention, while lower concentrations and pH-responsive degradation promote swelling and resorption under physiological conditions.

While HAp offers excellent biocompatibility and mechanical support, its low resorption rate can impede complete bone remodeling. Combining HAp with β -TCP in hydrogel-based scaffolds harnesses the complementary benefits of both bioceramics: HAp provides long-term structural support, whereas β -TCP facilitates early osteoconduction and degrades more rapidly in

physiological environments, allowing gradual replacement by new bone. The porous structure of GelMA hydrogels further enhances water infiltration and enzymatic degradation, enabling synchronized scaffold resorption and tissue regeneration. Lee et al. [296] demonstrated that incorporating β -TCP into a GelMA-HAp hydrogel improved mechanical strength, supported *in vitro* stem cell viability and osteogenic differentiation, and promoted bone regeneration in a rat calvarial defect model. This dual-bioceramic strategy shows strong potential for balancing scaffold stability and bioresorption in alveolar bone repair. This was supported by Zhuang et al. [297] who reported that nano- β -TCP/hydrogel scaffolds enhanced BMSC viability and osteogenesis, inferred from the increased ALP activity, mineralization, and upregulation of BMP-2 and p-ERK1/2. The scaffolds established a bioactive microenvironment with elevated cellular levels of inorganic phosphate and adenosine triphosphate, essential for initiating osteogenic signaling, with inhibition assays confirming ATP-dependent activation of the ERK1/2 pathway and BMP-2 expression as key mechanisms.

Cell-loaded biomimetic hydrogels represent a pivotal strategy in BTE, integrating scaffolds with stem cells, supporting cellular behavior that mirrors the morphological and functional traits of bone. Among these, GelMA hydrogels are particularly notable due to their prominent biocompatibility and capacity to support cell adhesion and proliferation. However, their intrinsic osteoinductive potential is limited. To overcome this limitation, GelMA hydrogels are often combined with bone marrow-derived stem cells (BMSCs), leveraging the regenerative capacity of stem cells to enhance osteogenesis and improve bone repair outcomes [289]. Li et al. [298] developed an injectable GelMA hydrogel hosting BMSCs, which was crosslinked *in situ* under UV light after injection into bone defects. The resulting biomaterial demonstrated good cytocompatibility and promoted substantial bone formation, vascularization, and mature tissue organization *in vivo*.

A key challenge of photoresponsive hydrogel systems lies in their dependence on photoinitiated crosslinking, commonly induced by ultraviolet (UV) light. This method generates free radicals, which can elicit cytotoxic effects, particularly when cells are encapsulated within the hydrogel matrix during UV exposure. Cellular viability may be significantly compromised due to direct photodamage and the accumulation of ROS, especially in dense or thick constructs where light penetration is inadequate and uneven [289, 299]. In this context, Goto et al. [299] proposed a safer crosslinking strategy utilizing riboflavin as a photosensitizer activated by visible light. This approach markedly improved cell viability by circumventing the deleterious effects associated with UV irradiation, including DNA damage and oxidative stress. *In vitro* studies demonstrated that KUSA-A1 cells—a murine mesenchymal stem cell line with strong osteogenic potential—encapsulated in 20% GelMA–riboflavin hydrogels and cultured under osteogenic conditions exhibited enhanced osteocalcin expression and advanced cellular maturation. These findings confirmed the osteoinductive potential of the riboflavin-crosslinked hydrogel scaffold.

5.1.2. Hydrogels with vascularization

Considering that bone is a highly vascularized tissue that relies on a well-organized vascular network for nutrient exchange and metabolic homeostasis, revascularization is a critical factor in treating bone defects. To promote vascularization and facilitate bone formation, hydrogels frequently need to be supplemented with pro-angiogenic and neuroregenerative growth factors [286, 289, 300, 301]. The incorporation of bioinorganic ions (e.g. Mg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , and Si^{4+}) into hydrogels has gained attention for promoting both angiogenesis and osteogenesis by acting as essential cofactors or signaling mediators[289]. For instance, Wu et al. [302] engineered injectable hydrogels composed of chitosan, silk fibroin, and glycerophosphate, incorporating copper-containing bioactive glass nanoparticles (Cu-BG NPs) to release Si, Ca, and Cu ions in a controlled and sustained manner. These ions synergistically promoted osteogenic differentiation of MC3T3-E1 cells and angiogenic activation of endothelial cells by upregulating key markers such as ALP, HIF-1 α , and VEGF. The hydrogel's porous structure facilitated cell infiltration, while chitosan modulated Cu ion release, preventing cytotoxicity and maintaining ion levels within a safe and effective range. Within a preclinical model of critical-size calvarial defects in rats, an optimized cell-free hydrogel composed of copper-doped bioactive glass (Cu-BG), chitosan (CH), silk fibroin (SF), and glycerophosphate (GP) achieved complete bone defect repair, accompanied by the formation of neovascularized and mineralized bone tissue. Similarly, an injectable hydrogel comprising phosphocreatine-functionalized chitosan and magnesium oxide nanoparticles (CSMP-MgO) demonstrated outstanding regenerative performance[303]. This system enabled sustained Mg^{2+} release, upregulated osteogenic gene expression, and promoted mineralization in MC3T3-E1 preosteoblasts. Furthermore, it markedly promoted the formation of capillary-like structures by HUVECs and facilitated robust new bone formation in a rat critical-size calvarial defect model, underscoring its potential for BTE applications.

Another concern about bone defects is that they often create a hypoxic microenvironment that impairs osteogenic differentiation and promotes inflammation through increased ROS production. To address this, Niu et al. [304] developed injectable, fast-gelling hydrogels based on NIPAAm copolymers with high oxygen preservation capacity to enhance cell survival and retention in ischemic tissues. The hydrogels solidified rapidly at 37 °C, maintained higher oxygen levels under hypoxic conditions, and supported the survival and proliferation of encapsulated MSCs, unlike control hydrogels with low oxygen preservation. In addition to enhancing cell viability, perfluorocarbon (PFC)-containing hydrogels—specifically PNHAM-PFC5 and PNHAM-PFC10—significantly promoted the paracrine activity of MSCs. This was evidenced by the upregulated expression of angiogenic (PDGFB) and prosurvival (IGF-1) factors over a 14-day period, suggesting a dual role for these hydrogels in supporting MSC survival and enhancing their therapeutic potential under hypoxic conditions [304].

Another agent that has been gaining attention is deferoxamine (DFO), an FDA-approved iron-chelating agent, known not only for its pro-angiogenic effect via upregulation of hypoxia-inducible

factor-1 α (HIF-1 α) but also for its immunomodulatory and anti-osteoclastogenic properties; however, its high water solubility can lead to burst release and local toxicity. To address this, Zhang et al. [305] developed a 3D-printed, biomimetic scaffold with hierarchical architecture, composed of PCL nanoparticles loaded with deferoxamine, MnCO nanosheets, a GelMA hydrogel phase, and a polylactide/hydroxyapatite framework (DMGP) (**Figure 9A**). Within the DMGP scaffold, the interaction between MnCO and endogenous H₂O₂ triggered a Fenton-like reaction, generating Mn²⁺ and CO, further promoting M2 macrophage polarization and synergistically enhancing HIF-1 α /VEGF signalling pathways. Gene and protein expression analyses confirmed significantly increased HIF-1 α and VEGF levels, resulting in robust neovascularization and efficient healing of critical-size femoral bone defects in vivo. This integrated strategy highlights the potential of combining immunomodulation, pro-angiogenic signalling, and controlled drug delivery in hydrogel design for the repair of large bone defects. Similarly, an injectable and resorbable hybrid hydrogel composed of poly(L-glutamic acid) grafted with tannic acid (PLG-g-TA), VEGF, and strontium-doped bioactive glass nanoparticles (Sr-BGNPs) (PLG-g-TA/VEGF/Sr-BGNPs) developed by Huang et al.[300], demonstrated significant angiogenic activity (**Figure 9B**). This was evidenced by a tube formation assay using Human Umbilical Vein Endothelial Cells (HUVECs), showing increased numbers of tubes and junctions, as well as greater total tube area and length compared to control groups. These findings confirm that the sustained release of VEGF, in combination with the bioactive ionic components released from Sr-BGNPs, significantly enhances neovascularization—an essential prerequisite for effective bone regeneration.

Importantly, bone repair depends on the sequential and coordinated action of growth factors like VEGF, platelet-derived growth factor-BB (PDGF-BB), and bone morphogenetic protein-2 (BMP-2), which regulate angiogenesis and osteogenesis. To replicate this natural healing cascade, Tang et al.[306] developed a self-healing "sandwich" hydrogel composed of quaternized chitosan and Pluronic® F127, designed to enable controlled, phase-specific release of three bioactive factors. This biomimetic system significantly enhanced vascularized bone regeneration while providing antibacterial protection in a critical-sized (8 mm) calvarial defect model in male Sprague-Dawley rats, underscoring its potential for effective and infection-resistant bone repair. Micro-CT and histological analyses demonstrated that sequential delivery of VEGF, PDGF-BB, and BMP-2 significantly improved bone volume, mineral density, trabecular architecture, and mineral apposition rate resulting in nearly complete defect closure and dense new bone formation 8 weeks post-implantation.

Figure 9. Multifunctional hydrogel-based platforms to treat bone defects. A) Schematic representation of a hydrogel-based scaffold with hierarchical architecture and osteoimmunomodulatory function, constructed using deferoxamine-loaded PCL nanoparticles (DFO@PCL NP), MnCO nanosheets, GelMA (DMGP), and a PLA/HA structural matrix designed to enhance bone regeneration. Reproduced with permission.[305] Copyright 2022, Wiley. B) In vitro osteogenic differentiation induced by the PLG-g-TA/VEGF/Sr-BGNPs hydrogel, demonstrating its bioactivity and potential for bone tissue engineering. Reproduced with permission.[300] Copyright 2024, Wiley. C) 3D printing of complex constructs using GelMA-PPy bioink, highlighting structural integrity and layer-dependent architecture (L indicates the number of printed layers). Reproduced with permission.[307] Copyright, 2023, Elsevier.

Recognizing the periosteum as a vital contributor to bone healing, owing to its high vascularity and regenerative potential, recent efforts in BTE have focused on developing biomimetic, tissue-engineered periosteum to better replicate the natural healing process. Yu et al. [308] designed a periosteal-bone substitute by incorporating a preosteoblast-derived matrix (pODM) into a GelMA hydrogel, forming a cell-free, engineered membrane that promoted BMSC adhesion, chemotaxis, and osteogenic differentiation. Within a preclinical model of non-healing radial bone defects in rabbits, the pODM/GelMA scaffold achieved complete bone and medullary cavity regeneration within 12 weeks. Similarly, Yang et al. [309] developed an organic-inorganic biomimetic periosteum (GA/HA-BG) to address the limitations of traditional periosteum-mimicking materials, which often fail to replicate the full biological functionality of native periosteum. Their strategy involved the hybridization of dopamine-conjugated gelatin and oxidized hyaluronan with micro/nano-structured bioactive glass (MNBG) to fabricate a co-crosslinked hydrogel membrane that mimics the extracellular matrix and exhibits self-adhesive properties to bone tissue. The incorporation of MNBG enhanced membrane stability and enabled the sustained release of bioactive ions (Ca^{2+} and SiO_4^{4-}), thereby promoting osteogenesis and angiogenesis. This was achieved by recruiting stem cells, inducing their osteogenic differentiation, and stimulating VEGF expression in endothelial cells via stimulation of the PI3K/Akt/HIF-1 α signaling cascade.

5.1.3. Hydrogels with osteoinductivity

The process of bone repair involves multiple stages and is tightly regulated by an orchestrated interplay of growth factors that govern cellular proliferation, differentiation, and tissue remodelling. A critical aspect of this process is osteoinductivity—the capacity of a material to recruit progenitor cells and induce their differentiation into osteoblasts [310]. To enhance bone regeneration, the direct application of exogenous growth factors has become a widely adopted strategy. Furthermore, combining two-dimensional (2D) nanomaterials, such as graphene oxide and black phosphorus, along with bioactive metal ions into scaffolds, has emerged as a promising approach. These components contribute to the creation of bioactive microenvironments that not only facilitate controlled growth factor release but also enhance osteoinductive potential, promote angiogenesis, and impart antimicrobial properties [289].

Osteoinductive factors play a crucial role in bone healing by activating signaling pathways that regulate bone formation and resorption. Essential signaling molecules such as bone morphogenetic proteins (BMPs) and parathyroid hormone (PTH) stimulate osteogenic differentiation—BMPs act via Smad and MAPK pathways to increase Runx-2 and Osx expression, while PTH influences bone mass through endocrine regulation [281]. Incorporating these factors into hydrogels has been reported to enhance their osteoinductive capacity, promoting stem cell differentiation and accelerating bone repair [289]. Diab et al. [311] demonstrated that an electrospun polycaprolactone nanofiber conduit in combination with a silk fibroin hydrogel for BMP-2 delivery effectively promoted the repair of critically-sized femoral defects in rats through osteoinduction. The silk hydrogel served as a biodegradable carrier for BMP-2, enabling sustained local delivery, which

enhanced osteogenic differentiation and bone formation over 12 weeks, as confirmed by imaging, histology, and improved biomechanical performance. Mechanistically, BMP-2 activated osteogenic pathways by upregulating transcription factors such as Runx-2 and Osx, while the complete degradation of the silk carrier likely facilitated tissue remodeling and bone integration [311]. Furthermore, to restore the osteoblast/osteoclast balance essential for osteoporotic bone healing, Kuang et al. [249] developed an innovative osteoinductive strategy utilizing an injectable hydrogel (DHCP-10PIP/d) engineered for dual-mode, near-infrared (NIR)-triggered delivery of parathyroid hormone (PTH). This system enabled both sustained basal release and on-demand, pulsatile release of PTH upon NIR irradiation, thereby promoting osteogenic differentiation of bone marrow stromal cells (BMSCs) and osteoclastogenesis. The resulting balanced bone remodeling led to significant improvements in bone mineral density, bone volume, and defect healing in an ovariectomized rat model. These findings highlight the potential of spatiotemporally controlled PTH delivery to enhance osteoinduction in compromised bone environments.

Incorporating metal ions into hydrogels has shown promise in enhancing scaffold performance. A 3D-printed composite hydrogel scaffold composed of sodium alginate, gelatin, and α -tricalcium phosphate (α -TCP), supplemented with varying concentrations of strontium ions (Sr^{2+}), exhibited notable swelling behavior—expanding up to 600% of its original volume within 4 hours in PBS at 25 °C [223]. Mechanical properties were also improved, with the 0.5 wt% Sr^{2+} group achieving a compressive strength of 2.05 ± 0.13 MPa, compared to 1.78 ± 0.29 MPa in the control. In vitro, BMSCs cultured on the developed scaffolds presented high viability, enhanced proliferation (CCK-8 assay), and upregulated osteogenic and angiogenic gene expression, particularly in the 0.5 wt % Sr^{2+} group. In vivo, implantation in 5-mm critical-sized rat skull defects showed significantly enhanced bone regeneration after 8 weeks. The 0.5 wt % Sr^{2+} scaffolds achieved the highest bone volume fraction, mineral density, and surface area, accompanied by dense collagen-rich bone formation and increased CD31 expression, indicating both osteogenic and angiogenic enhancement. Nevertheless, although strategies that enable the controlled and sustained release of ions are critical to maintaining their concentration within an optimal therapeutic window and avoiding cytotoxic effects. In this regard, Liu et al. [253] reported a therapeutic approach for periodontitis treatment based on combining the antibacterial and osteogenic potential of zeolitic imidazolate framework-8 (ZIF-8) with the favorable properties of gelatin methacryloyl (GelMA) hydrogel. In this context, ZIF-8, a zinc-based metal-organic framework, enables sustained Zn^{2+} release, promoting antibacterial activity against pathogens like *P. gingivalis* and enhancing osteogenic differentiation through increased alkaline phosphatase activity and mineralization. GelMA, an injectable and photopolymerizable scaffold, mimics the ECM and adapts to irregular periodontal defects. Its arginine–glycine–aspartic acid (RGD) peptide sequence motifs and MMP-sensitive sequences facilitate cell adhesion and remodeling, while UV crosslinking ensures stable in situ localization.

In addition to bioactive hydrogels, there is growing interest in incorporating 2D nanomaterials—such as graphene oxide (GO), black phosphorus (BP) nanosheets, and nanotubes (NTs)—to enhance mechanical and biological performance. Low concentrations of GO improved the structure and mechanical strength of silk fibroin (SF)/GO hydrogels and supported bone marrow stromal cell differentiation [312]. Similarly, Huang et al. [313] developed a black phosphorus nanosheet (BPN)-based, photo-crosslinked GelMA hydrogel that promotes bone regeneration by releasing phosphate ions, which sequester calcium from the environment to enhance biomineralization and mechanical properties. This system stimulated osteogenesis via the BMP/Runx2 pathway in vitro and significantly improved bone repair in a rabbit model.

5.1.4. Stimuli-responsive and 3D-bioprinting hydrogels

Three-dimensional printing has become a promising approach in bone regeneration, offering the ability to create patient-tailored scaffolds with controllable mechanical behavior and customizable geometries [223, 224, 293]. This approach enables precise control over hydrogel volume, shape, and internal architecture, enhancing structural integration and regenerative outcomes. More recently, the integration of stimuli-responsive components into 3D-printed scaffolds has expanded their functionality, enabling on-demand drug delivery, dynamic structural adaptation, and the activation of biological responses at different healing stages [291, 292].

Pan et al. [314] developed a microRNA-activated hydrogel scaffold (MAHS) to promote bone regeneration by synchronizing scaffold degradation with the sustained release of osteoinductive microRNA (miR-29b). These scaffolds, fabricated by 3D plotting using gelatin–alginate hydrogels and crosslinked at varying degrees, were designed to gradually degrade while releasing miR-29b complexed with protective gold nanoparticles (miR/NPs), thus mimicking the natural bone healing cascade. The term miRNA-activated scaffold refers to a biomaterial platform that provides structural support and delivers regulatory microRNAs directly to the cellular environment, influencing gene expression to promote osteogenic differentiation. Importantly, a key challenge in designing 3D-bioprinting hydrogels for bone substitutes is addressing the limitations of extrusion-based bioprinting, particularly in structural fidelity and fabrication efficiency. Doyle et al. [315] developed a high-throughput 3D sacrificial printing platform to create reproducible cellular hydrogels containing bioactive particles such as TCP, hyaluronic acid or natural coral. These constructs maintained cell viability, metabolism, and osteogenic differentiation over 7 days, as shown by collagen deposition, calcium uptake, and matrix formation. The platform enabled rapid, non-destructive screening of bone graft materials, offering a scalable, cost- and time-efficient approach for in vitro evaluation.

Considering the critical role of biofunctionality in 3D-bioprinted scaffolds, Zhang et al. [316] developed a multilayered hydrogel scaffold mimicking the zonal architecture of osteochondral (OC) tissue, composed of a cartilage-like top layer (0% nHA), an intermediate calcified cartilage layer (40% nHA), and a subchondral bone layer (70% nHA), all embedded in a robust double-

network hydrogel matrix. The gradient scaffold showed improved mechanical properties, with compressive strength up to 900 kPa and enhanced tensile strength. In vivo, BMSC-loaded scaffolds implanted in rat knee OC defects resulted in complete defect filling and formation of hyaline-like cartilage and subchondral bone after 12 weeks. Micro-CT and histological analyses confirmed superior bone regeneration, tissue morphology, and integration. These findings, combined with advances in in situ 3D bioprinting, highlight the translational potential of biofunctional, multilayered constructs for clinical applications. Li et al. [317] demonstrated the potential of in situ 3D bioprinting to repair large segmental bone defects, moving beyond static scaffold fabrication to dynamic, patient-specific treatments performed directly at the injury site. They filled complex defects in swine models with high precision and structural fidelity by combining rapid 3D scanning, reverse-engineering software, and robotic-assisted printing with a bio-ink composed of alginate and PEGDA.

An illustrative example of stimuli-responsive hydrogels is the development of a 3D-printed MXene-integrated composite hydrogel that combines photothermal antibacterial activity and osteogenic capacity to address the complex clinical challenge of infected, irregularly shaped bone defects[291]. Upon NIR irradiation, the MXene component was shown to generate localized heat, effectively eradicating both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, while the scaffold's composition—including Sr^{2+} ions and β -TCP—supports bone regeneration, demonstrating how external stimuli can be leveraged to trigger therapeutic responses in situ. Beyond light responsiveness, recent advances in 3D bioprinting of conductive hydrogels have enabled the fabrication of increasingly complex biomimetic structures. However, achieving optimal printability and biofunctionality remains a challenge [224, 291]. To overcome this, a GelMA-polypyrrole (GelMA-PPy) bioink was developed using a triple cross-linking approach—thermal, photoinitiated, and ionic—which produced a stable, shear-thinning ink with high structural fidelity and cytocompatibility (**Figure 9C**) [307]. When combined with electrical stimulation, the bioink significantly enhanced osteogenic differentiation of hBMSCs by activating the NOTCH, MAPK, and SMAD signaling pathways, demonstrating strong potential for bone tissue engineering.

While biomimetic and bioactive scaffolds offer promise for regenerative signaling, recent advances have expanded their application to more complex challenges, such as infection-related bone defects[286, 289]. In these cases, promoting osteogenesis alone is insufficient; effective regeneration also requires control of microbial contamination. This has spurred interest in stimuli-responsive scaffolds that provide both osteogenic and antimicrobial effects. A notable example is a 3D-printed hierarchical PEEK scaffold with a pH-sensitive “pDA–Ag–pDA” coating, which releases silver ions in acidic, bacteria-associated environments[318]. This targeted response preserves biocompatibility, eliminates pathogens, and supports bone ingrowth and osseointegration—demonstrating the potential of infection-responsive implants.

5.2. Bone defect models for preclinical evaluation of hydrogel implants

Bone defect healing is a complex process governed by cellular, molecular, and mechanical interactions. Animal models play a vital role in assessing bone substitute biomaterials, with a key consideration being whether the defect can heal spontaneously. Critical-sized defects, which do not regenerate naturally within the animal's lifetime, are particularly valuable for distinguishing biomaterial-induced regeneration from natural healing [319]. Common defect sites for bone regeneration studies include the calvaria, femur, tibia, and ulna. Rodents are widely used in early-stage research due to their low cost, ease of handling, and rapid bone turnover. In nude mice, a 3 mm femoral or 4 mm calvarial defect is considered critical-sized [319]. These defects are surgically created under anesthesia with minimal trauma to assess the performance of bone substitute materials. For example, Zhang et al. [305] developed a critical-sized femoral defect model in Sprague–Dawley rats by creating 6 mm × 6 mm cylindrical defects in the femoral diaphysis to evaluate hydrogel-based scaffolds for osteogenesis (**Figure 10A**). The scaffolds were implanted into the bone defects, and regeneration was evaluated at 4- and 8-weeks post-surgery using micro-CT, histological analysis, and immunofluorescence (**Figure 10B**). Untreated defects exhibited minimal healing and structural deformation. In contrast, defects treated with scaffolds demonstrated significantly enhanced bone formation, increased vascularization, and active tissue remodeling. These outcomes were supported by imaging data and the expression profiles of osteogenic and inflammatory markers.

Another widely used model for evaluating bone regeneration involves the creation of 5 mm full-thickness critical-size defects in the rat calvaria. Huang et al. [300] employed this model to investigate bone regeneration following treatment with various hydrogel formulations. Among the tested groups, the hydrogel incorporating VEGF and strontium-doped bioactive glass nanoparticles exhibited the most effective bone repair, achieving nearly complete defect closure by 8 weeks. Micro-CT analysis revealed significantly increased bone volume and density compared to controls, highlighting the strong regenerative potential of the composite hydrogel (**Figure 10C**). Similarly, Zhang et al. [320] utilized the same 5 mm defect model to evaluate the osteogenic efficacy of different hydrogel systems. In their study, 60 μ L of hydrogel precursor solution was applied directly into each defect site and photopolymerized in situ using 450 nm blue light for 30 seconds, enabling the hydrogel to conform precisely to the defect geometry and form a stable, integrative scaffold. Using this approach, a calcium phosphate-loaded hydrogel exhibited superior bone regeneration, evidenced by significantly higher surface coverage, bone volume fraction (BV/TV), and bone mineral density (BMD), compared to the control and other hydrogel groups (**Figure 10D**). Notably, while the HAp-loaded hydrogel achieved approximately 53% new bone coverage at 8 weeks, the calcium phosphate-loaded hydrogel markedly enhanced bone formation, reaching 88% in a rat cranial defect model.

Despite their widespread use, small animal models possess inherent limitations due to substantial differences in bone remodeling mechanisms compared to humans—most notably, the absence of

a fully developed Haversian system. Furthermore, these models typically involve young, systemically healthy animals, which does not accurately reflect the clinical characteristics of patients with critical-size bone defects. In contrast, large animal models—such as rabbits, dogs, goats, and particularly sheep—demonstrate closer physiological and anatomical resemblance to human bone with respect to structure, mechanical loading, and remodeling dynamics. Nonetheless, their use entails significant challenges, including elevated costs, more demanding housing conditions, and heightened ethical considerations.

Figure 10. Bone regeneration in critical-sized femoral, calvarial, and periodontal bone defect models. A) Digital images showing scaffold implantation into a 6 mm critical-sized femoral diaphysis defect in Sprague–Dawley rats. B) Representative 3D micro-CT reconstructions demonstrating bone regeneration around femoral defects. Reproduced with permission [305]. Copyright 2022, Wiley. C) 3D reconstructed micro-CT images of calvarial bone following hydrogel implantation in a 5 mm critical-sized cranial defect. Reproduced with permission [300]. 2024, Wiley. D) In vivo bone regeneration in the calvarial defect model. Histological evaluation at 8 weeks post-surgery using H&E and Masson’s trichrome staining reveals new bone formation and tissue organization across treatment groups. Reproduced with permission.[320] Copyright 2025, Wiley. E) Ligature-induced periodontal bone defect model. 3D reconstruction images of maxillary alveolar bone at 4 weeks, and corresponding 2D images showing vertical bone loss and regeneration outcomes in different groups. Reproduced with permission [253]. 2022, Elsevier.

Dental and craniofacial applications of hydrogel scaffolds necessitate specialized in vivo models to accurately replicate the complex anatomical and pathological conditions of these regions. Periodontal bone defect models, in particular, are commonly established either through ligature-induced periodontitis or surgical procedures to mimic alveolar bone loss around natural dentition. For example, a rat model of periodontal bone loss was developed by placing orthodontic ligation wires around the maxillary first molars, followed by daily subgingival injections of lipopolysaccharide to induce localized inflammation and progressive alveolar bone resorption [253]. After a four-week induction period, the animals were treated with GelMA hydrogels, either alone or loaded with zinc (GelMA-ZH), which were injected directly into the periodontal pockets and polymerized in situ (**Figure 10E**). Micro-CT analysis revealed significant alveolar bone resorption and root exposure in the periodontitis group. In contrast, both hydrogel-treated groups showed improved bone preservation, with GelMA-ZH yielding the most pronounced effect. This group exhibited a significantly reduced cemento-enamel junction–alveolar bone crest distance (CEJ-ABC) and an increased bone volume / total volume (BV/TV ratio), approaching healthy control levels. These results suggest that GelMA-ZH hydrogel effectively promotes alveolar bone regeneration and mitigates inflammatory bone loss, underscoring its potential for periodontal tissue engineering. Likewise, peri-implant bone defect models are employed to study bone loss around dental implants, effectively simulating peri-implantitis and its treatment strategies[321]. These models facilitate the evaluation of hydrogel-based therapies in infected environments and are particularly valuable for testing multifunctional scaffolds with combined antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and osteoinductive properties.

Nevertheless, despite their utility in investigating periodontal and peri-implant regeneration, animal models present several limitations. For instance, ligature-induced models, although commonly used, only mimic certain aspects of the disease and fall short of replicating the chronic and multifactorial nature of human conditions [321]. Such models often depend on mechanical plaque retention and, in some cases, inoculation with a single bacterial species—an approach that does not reflect the complex polymicrobial biofilms typical of human periodontitis or peri-implantitis. Consequently, these models may oversimplify host–microbiome interactions and fail to represent the dynamic microbial shifts and ecological diversity observed in clinical settings. While animal models are essential for validating bone substitutes, they pose ethical, financial, and translational challenges. Species-specific differences in bone healing, immune response, and anatomy hinder direct extrapolation to human outcomes. As a result, ex vivo human bone defect models are gaining attention as intermediate platforms. Kluter et al. [322] developed such a model using femoral head specimens from hip replacement surgeries. Cylindrical bone sections (20 mm × 7 mm) with a central defect (6 mm × 5 mm) were filled with collagen type I hydrogel. The model remained viable for 28 days, supporting cell proliferation, migration, and osteogenic marker expression. These systems offer a promising tool for preliminary biomaterial screening, though standardized protocols and further validation are required.

In summary, selecting an appropriate bone defect model should be guided by the target clinical application, the biological question, and the translational relevance of the species and defect site. Small animal models are valuable for initial screening, while large animals and advanced ex vivo systems play a crucial role in bridging toward human application. Integrating these models into the development pipeline of hydrogel-based scaffolds is key to optimizing their performance and accelerating clinical translation.

5.3. Commercial landscape and regulatory considerations

Although hydrogel-based systems have demonstrated promising outcomes in bone and periodontal regeneration, their translation into routine clinical practice remains limited. Nevertheless, recent clinical studies underscore their therapeutic potential. For instance, RGD-modified hydrogels used in conjunction with minimally invasive surgical techniques have been shown to enhance bone fill, attachment gain, and the expression of osteogenic markers such as BMP-2, thereby supporting their efficacy in periodontal regeneration [323]. Similarly, DEXGEL Bone—an injectable formulation that integrates Bonelike® granules with a dextrin-based hydrogel—has proven to be safe, user-friendly, and effective in enhancing implant stability and promoting bone regeneration in alveolar ridge preservation procedures [324]. In the neurosurgical field, hyaluronan-based hydrogels, either alone or loaded with BMP-2, have successfully facilitated bone healing in human cranial defects, exhibiting regenerative outcomes comparable to autologous bone grafts without associated adverse effects [325]. Collectively, these findings highlight the clinical feasibility, safety, and versatility of hydrogel-based systems for bone regeneration across various anatomical contexts.

Despite notable advancements, the commercial landscape for hydrogel-based bone substitutes remains limited. Only a few products—such as Gelrin C™—have progressed into clinical trials. In contrast, most commercially available hydrogels, including Mebiol® Gel, HyStem®, Corning® Matrigel®, PuraMatrix™, and Biogelx™, are largely confined to preclinical research due to persistent challenges related to mechanical strength, manufacturing scalability, and regulatory compliance [289]. These hydrogels are primarily utilized for 3D cell culture, drug delivery, and in vitro modeling, capitalizing on their biocompatibility and ECM-mimicking properties. However, their translation into widespread clinical use is hindered by insufficient in vivo performance data and the absence of simplified, cost-effective delivery methods that align with surgical workflows.

The clinical adoption of hydrogel-based scaffolds is further constrained by regulatory hurdles concerning safety, quality assurance, and the lack of standardized evaluation protocols. For hydrogel systems—especially injectable formulations intended for bone regeneration—to achieve clinical viability, they must exhibit controlled degradation, reproducible biocompatibility, and adaptability to patient-specific anatomical and physiological conditions. Ideal systems should be cost-efficient, user-friendly, and designed to support bone healing through minimally invasive

procedures, with efficacy validated in large-animal models. To accelerate clinical translation, advances in 3D/4D printing, bioresponsive crosslinking, and scalable fabrication techniques must be integrated with evolving regulatory frameworks. These frameworks should be optimized to accommodate multifunctional and personalized hydrogel platforms, thereby facilitating their transition from bench to bedside [290].

6. IMPLANTABLE HYDROGELS FOR HEALTH MONITORING

Implantable hydrogel patches are changing the way health is monitored, offering a seamless connection between technology and the human body. These patches, built from soft, water-rich materials, mimic biological tissues, making them comfortable and effective for long-term use. Scientists have recently enhanced their design, improving conductivity and durability to ensure they provide accurate real-time data. One of the most exciting developments is in cardiac monitoring. Researchers have engineered hydrogel patches that adhere to the heart and transmit electrophysiological signals, aiding in the detection of irregularities and even supporting recovery after myocardial infarction. Similarly, in diabetes management, smart hydrogel patches have emerged as a non-invasive solution for glucose monitoring. Transparent and adhesive, they provide continuous readings without the discomfort of frequent blood testing. These patches are also making strides in neurological applications, where they act as highly sensitive interfaces for detecting brain signals.

6.1. Biochemical monitoring

Hydrogel patches have emerged as a promising tool for monitoring a wide range of biological parameters. One of their most impactful applications is continuous glucose tracking in which by incorporating glucose-sensitive moieties into the hydrogel matrix, these devices deliver real-time, high-precision measurements that simplify daily management for diabetic patients and can significantly improve glycemic control and quality of life. For example, Guo et al. recently reported a zwitterionic thermo-glucose-sensitive “skin-like” sensor featuring a three-layer “sandwich” architecture—two hydrogel sensing layers (zwitterionic carboxylbetaine copolymerized with NIPAAm and MPBA) electrically isolated by an elastomeric film (**Figure 11A**). By assigning distinct electrical readouts— $|\Delta R_0|$ for strain, $|\Delta R_2 - R_0|$ for temperature and $|\Delta R_1 - R_2|$ for glucose concentration, their design effectively decoupled cross-talk among signals, enabling continuous, real-time monitoring of infection, swelling and blood glucose at diabetic wound sites [326]. In vivo tests further demonstrated that this conformal patch not only delivered stable multimodal feedback but also accelerated chronic wound closure compared to commercial dressings. While electrical transduction relies on conductivity changes and thermo-responsive mechanics, molecular imprinting offers an alternative sensing strategy by creating template-shaped cavities within the hydrogel for selective analyte capture and optical readout. As such, Giovanninni et al. developed a molecularly imprinted, boronic-acid-functionalized hydrogel that transduced glucose binding into a fluorescence decrease, achieving robust, enzyme-free quantification through imprinting-enhanced specificity rather than electrical sensing [327].

Engineered hydrogel sensors, featuring tailored molecular recognition and multifunctional architectures, also enable sensitive, non-invasive, and multiplexed detection of cancer biomarkers to enhance early diagnosis and improve treatment outcomes [328]. In this sense, a pH-responsive, tumor-selective electroconductive hydrogel sensor (CD-PNB@PVA) was engineered so that acidic tumor microenvironments cleave diol–diol crosslinks in carbon-dot nanoparticles, boosting conductivity and producing markedly higher strain and pressure signals in cancer cells versus normal cells [329]. Integrated with a wireless system and smartphone interface, this implantable hydrogel reliably monitored tumor presence in vivo by transmitting real-time sensing data from tumor-bearing mice. This seamless smartphone connectivity not only streamlines data acquisition and user interaction but also exemplifies the shift toward mobile, point-of-care diagnostics. Hu et al. developed a wearable, mobile phone-compatible device featuring an upconversion luminescent probe enclosed within a 3D polyacrylamide hydrogel matrix to achieve near-infrared-excited, multiplex chromatic sensing of urea via the inner-filter effect [330].

Figure 11. Hydrogels for health monitoring. A) Schematic illustration of a sandwich-structured sensor featuring a multifunctional zwitterionic interface for simultaneous multi-sensing capabilities and accelerated healing of diabetic wounds. Reproduced with permission.[326] Copyright 2021, Wiley. B) Real-time monitoring of sweat during exercise using the M-hydrogel sensor. The sensor was worn on the thigh during squats, with Bluetooth communication via an ankle-mounted device; current changes were displayed on a smartphone; sweat pH was measured through hydrogel resistance changes and validated with pH paper, showing correlation with exercise intensity. Reproduced with permission. [331] Copyright 2021, Wiley. C) Schematic of an AI-powered colorimetric biosensor system compatible with smartphones, featuring a hyaluronic acid hydrogel bioreactor and an agar hydrogel for signal amplification for bacterial detection, with results analyzed via the YOLOv5 algorithm. Reproduced with permission [332]. Copyright 2024,

Elsevier. D) Schematic illustration of GNT hydrogel fabrication and its synergistic hemostatic, antibacterial, and anti-inflammatory effects that promote healing of full-thickness oral mucosal defects. [333] Copyright 2022, American Chemical Society. E) Detection of subtle motions using the hydrogel sensor: resistance signal curves during wrist bending and various locomotion states (slow walking, walking, and running), along with relative resistance changes corresponding to different intensities of cheek blowing [334]. Copyright 2024, Elsevier.

6.2. Physiological and electrophysiological parameters monitoring

Hydrogel sensors for physiological state monitoring harness stimuli-responsive polymers and conductive fillers to transduce changes in temperature, mechanical deformation, and bioelectrical activity into reliable signals, enabling continuous, skin-conformal tracking of key health metrics. Thermosensitive hydrogels, predominantly composed of poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) (PNIPAM), undergo a reversible shift from hydrophilic to hydrophobic at their lower critical solution temperature (LCST, ~ 34 °C), inducing pronounced volume contraction and optical changes that are ideal for on-demand drug release and precise physiological temperature monitoring [335]. However, during this phase transition PNIPAM networks often suffer from water expulsion, leading to dehydration, adhesion loss, and mechanical weakening, and conventional antidehydration measures, such as polyol or salt additives, only limit surface evaporation without preventing shrinkage. To address these drawbacks, Zhang et al. engineered a gelatin-mesh-reinforced PNIPAM hydrogel (NAGP-Gel), in which the gelatin's helical scaffold traps water molecules and confines polymer-chain movement [335]. The result is the achievement of water retention, volume stability, skin adhesion, and signal reliability across the LCST, overcoming the key limitations of traditional PNIPAM sensors. Muscle-movement monitoring is another compelling application of hydrogel sensors, as these soft, water-rich ionic conductors—built from three-dimensional polymer networks reinforced with conductive nanomaterials—conform seamlessly to skin and transduce mechanical deformation into electrical signals [336]. For example, a recent wearable MXene-polyacrylic acid/polyvinyl alcohol (MXene-PAA/PVA) hydrogel combined the pH sensitivity of PAA/PVA with the metallic conductivity of MXene nanosheets; bending or stretching the forearm altered the gel's interconnected ion-electron pathways, producing proportional resistance changes, while sweat acidity triggered pH-driven swelling that reveals muscle fatigue [331] (**Figure 11B**). Integrated with a Bluetooth module, this multifunctional patch delivered synchronized electromechanical and biochemical feedback in real time, demonstrating how rational hydrogel design can enable noninvasive, dynamic monitoring of muscle activity.

Building on these conductive-based strategies, hydrogel platforms can likewise serve as soft, conformal electrodes for capturing bioelectrical activity. By embedding conductive networks such as metal nanowires, PEDOT:PSS, or graphene flakes into a hydrated polymer matrix, these hydrogels can record electrophysiological signals like electrocardiogram (ECG) and local field potentials with high fidelity and minimal motion artifact. Among conductive hydrogels, PEDOT:PSS has been reported to combine excellent conductivity, stability, and processability with

tunable network structures, which are achieved via crosslinking, ionic or photo-induced gelation, and versatile fabrication methods (e.g., spinning, printing, molding) to precisely tailor their microstructure and performance [337]. For instance, Yu et al. introduced a PSS-chain engineering approach in which sodium 4-styrenesulfonate copolymerized with N-(hydroxymethyl)acrylamide yielded a thermally cross-linkable P(SS-co-NHMAA) matrix that, upon oxidative polymerization with EDOT and subsequent dry-annealing/rehydration, formed highly conductive, soft, tough, and stretchable PSN hydrogels (up to $1850 \text{ S}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ conductivity, $>50\%$ strain, $\sim 4 \text{ MPa}$ modulus, $\sim 400 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ toughness). By tuning the PSS/PNHMAA ratio, they precisely modulated electrical, mechanical, and swelling behavior, and, via low-temperature lyophilization/redispersion, produced a 3D-printable bioink for direct-ink-writing of soft skin electrodes, which demonstrated electromyographic recording performance compared to commercial electrodes [338].

6.3. Disease Detection

Leveraging their tissue-like softness and tunable chemistry, hydrogel sensors also can enable real-time disease detection by transducing specific biomarkers and bioelectrical signals, ranging from early infection markers and cardiac electrophysiology to pre-seizure neural activity, thereby empowering timely diagnosis, personalized treatment strategies, and continuous patient monitoring [339]. To address both infection monitoring and safe antibacterial therapy in wound care, Chen et al. engineered a multifunctional alginate-based hydrogel dressing (Au NCs@AIPH/BTB) that combines real-time pH sensing with synergistic photothermal and free-radical treatment [340]. By embedding bromothymol blue (BTB) within a poly(acrylic anhydride–modified oxidized sodium alginate) network, the dressing visibly reports wound acidity—an indicator of bacterial infection—via color change. Simultaneously, gold nanocages loaded with the stable free-radical generator AIPH serve as both NIR-responsive heat sources and radical producers, in which mild laser irradiation accelerated AIPH decomposition and photothermal heating to deliver potent antibacterial action at lower temperatures, minimizing collateral tissue damage. Both in vitro and in vivo tests confirmed that Au NCs@AIPH/BTB exhibited excellent biocompatibility, effective bacterial eradication, and accelerated wound healing under near-infrared light. Similarly, considering that pathogenic bacteria secrete hyaluronidase (HAase), which degrades hyaluronic-acid (HA) matrices and serves as a highly specific biomarker for differentiating Gram-positive from Gram-negative infections, Cui et al. engineered an AI-assisted, smartphone-based colorimetric biosensor comprising a CPRG-loaded HA hydrogel “bioreactor” and a β -galactosidase–loaded agar “signal generator” [332] (**Figure 11C**). Bacterial HAase cleaved the HA matrix in proportion to cell concentration, releasing CPRG that β -gal converts into a visible color change; a custom YOLOv5 algorithm quantified hue shifts from a phone image to infer bacterial load. This simple, instrument-free assay achieved a 10 CFU/mL detection limit in under 60 minutes, meets WHO’s “ASSURED” criteria in food, antimicrobial-susceptibility, and clinical samples, and exemplifies how combining hydrogel chemistry with AI-powered imaging can transform point-of-care bacterial diagnostics.

Oral-cavity monitoring is another disease that demands bioelectronics that adhere in wet, dynamic environments without excessive swelling. Full-thickness oral mucosal defects, for example, is caused by trauma or lesion resection that are plagued by severe bleeding, high infection risk, and slow healing. To address this, Zhu et al. engineered a dual-crosslinked GelMA–nanoclay–tannic acid (GNT) hydrogel, using UV-mediated covalent bonding followed by tannic-acid immersion aimed at developing a minimally swelling, strongly adhesive matrix capable of rapid blood coagulation and exhibiting robust antibacterial and anti-inflammatory properties [333] (**Figure 11D**). In rodent and rabbit models, GNT hydrogels outperformed commercial membranes by accelerating mucosal defect closure, modulating key inflammation pathways, and offering a safe, facile strategy for oral wound repair. In another study, Pan et al. designed a miniaturized, tooth-adherent RF sensor that used an agarose hydrogel interlayer loaded with AgNPs–chlorhexidine (CHL) between split-ring resonators to both detect saliva H₂S—via the formation of Ag₂S, which shifts the sensor’s resonant frequency—and release CHL for on-site antibacterial therapy [341]. This wireless platform achieved a low detection limit, a broad dynamic range, and high selectivity, accurately distinguishing periodontitis patients from healthy individuals in real saliva samples. In the same context, Hu et al. engineered a structural-color hydrogel by incorporating a disulfide-containing crosslinker (BISS) into a polyacrylamide matrix and templating it as a photonic crystal [342]. They demonstrated real-time, in situ monitoring of VSC production by *P. gingivalis* that correlated with turbidimetric growth curves, and validated exhaled-breath measurements in halitosis patients against clinical diagnoses. By arranging hydrogels of different starting hues into an array, the system distinguished varying oral-health states for periodontitis risk assessment. Finally, a smartphone app employing colorimetric analysis of captured images enabled rapid, low-cost point-of-care testing of exhaled VSCs, offering a sensitive, user-friendly screening tool for periodontitis.

6.4. Respiratory and sleep monitoring

Hydrogel-based humidity sensors, with their rapid moisture absorption and skin-conformal design, can also enable continuous real-time monitoring of exhaled-air moisture to distinguish breathing patterns and support the treatment and monitoring of disorders such as sleep apnea, asthma, and pneumonia. For the purpose of accurate monitoring of respiration and body posture, Liu et al. developed a multifunctional wearable sensor using a hydrogel electrolyte composed of polyvinyl alcohol, sodium alginate, and starch, enabling dual-mode sensing through resistance and capacitance outputs [334] (**Figure 11E**). This design allowed independent detection of mechanical deformation and temperature changes, while also serving as a soft supercapacitor for self-powered operation. The sensor demonstrated excellent sensitivity, durability, and environmental stability, with strain responses up to 2500% and over 90% capacitance retention after 700 cycles. Integrated with a deep learning algorithm, it achieved a 99.259% accuracy in posture recognition and was successfully applied for real-time monitoring of nasal airflow and mechanical vibrations in the neck and hands. Notably, it enabled the non-invasive diagnosis of obstructive sleep apnea syndrome. Although promising, it is important to highlight that most existing sensors monitor only

a single body part or physiological signal, limiting their accuracy and applicability in real-time respiration monitoring.

In this context, wearable electronics have attracted considerable interest in the field of personalized healthcare. Liu et al. exemplified this approach by engineering a hydrogel sensor that operates through both resistive and capacitive mechanisms using a multifunctional cellulose-based hydrogel, offering simultaneous and independent detection of mechanical and thermal stimuli [343]. The sensor was fabricated using a double cross-linked cellulose hydrogel (CH-GT), enhanced with tannic acid, glycerin, water, and NaCl, to improve mechanical toughness and environmental stability. Featuring a dielectric layer sandwiched between two hydrogel layers, the device operates via ionic resistance for temperature detection and parallel-plate capacitance for sensing mechanical vibrations. This enables independent tracking of nasal airflow, thoracoabdominal movements, and arterial pulse signals. The sensor demonstrated high accuracy and durability in real-time monitoring of obstructive sleep apnea syndrome (OSAS), highlighting its potential as a robust, comfortable, and reliable solution for continuous multimodal respiratory health monitoring.

7. CHALLENGES TO CLINICAL TRANSLATION

The clinical translation of implantable hydrogel coatings (IHGs) is hindered by several critical challenges. One of the primary issues is poor adhesion to medical device surfaces, particularly metallic substrates, due to the mechanical mismatch between the soft hydrogel layer and the rigid implant surface. This mismatch often leads to delamination and detachment of the hydrogel coatings under mechanical stress, especially in high-load-bearing applications such as orthopedic implants and cardiovascular stents. Moreover, many current attachment strategies rely on cytotoxic solvents or chemical agents, which can impede regulatory approval and compromise biocompatibility. Consequently, there is a pressing need for safer and more effective methods to enhance hydrogel adhesion for implantable applications. Plasma technology has emerged as a promising alternative—offering a dry, clean, and environmentally friendly surface modification technique. By tailoring the surface chemistry and topography of the implant material, plasma treatment can significantly improve the adhesion and durability of hydrogel coatings, thereby enabling the development of robust and sustainable solid–hydrogel hybrid systems [108, 109, 111]. Excessive swelling of hydrogels following coating can compromise their adhesion to implant surfaces and alter their mechanical properties, potentially resulting in delamination or impaired in vivo function. Therefore, precise control of swelling—achieved through modulation of crosslinking density or incorporation of composite materials—is essential to ensure coating stability and maintain overall device performance.

The incorporation of hydrophobic drugs into hydrophilic hydrogel matrices poses a significant formulation challenge due to their limited solubility and poor dispersion. To overcome this, hydrogels are frequently modified to introduce amphiphilic characteristics or incorporate

hydrophobic domains capable of encapsulating and releasing poorly water-soluble drugs. For instance, hydrogels grafted with methyl methacrylate or other hydrophobic moieties have demonstrated effective loading and controlled release of such compounds via hydrophobic interactions and domain entrapment [344]. This strategy holds promise for the development of next-generation hydrogel coatings on medical implants, facilitating both robust surface adhesion and localized delivery of hydrophobic therapeutics.

Sterilization remains a major challenge in the clinical translation of hydrogel-coated medical implants. Traditional sterilization methods—such as heat, radiation, or chemical exposure—can compromise the mechanical integrity and functional performance of hydrogel coatings. For instance, autoclaving or gamma irradiation may induce hydrogel shrinkage, water loss, or crosslinking disruption, thereby impairing biocompatibility and drug-release capabilities. In this context, a recent study by Ghosh et al. [345] investigated the stability of nanogel-based hydrogel coatings composed of N-isopropylacrylamide-co-aminopropyl methacrylamide (NIPAM-co-APMA). These coatings were applied to clinically relevant implant substrates, including polypropylene (PP), polyetheretherketone (PEEK), titanium (Ti), and glass, and subsequently subjected to various sterilization methods. The study found that coatings on polymeric substrates (PP and PEEK) retained their antifouling and antibacterial properties post-sterilization, whereas coatings on metallic and inorganic surfaces demonstrated reduced stability and performance. These discrepancies were attributed to differences in surface energy, bonding interactions, and the hydrogel network's sensitivity to sterilization conditions. These findings highlight the necessity for sterilization protocols that are specifically optimized to maintain both the functional integrity and microbiological safety of hydrogel-coated implants.

8. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE OUTLOOK

Multifunctional hydrogel implants are emerging as versatile platforms for a wide range of biomedical, drug delivery, and diagnostic applications. The integration of tailorable design strategies, advanced biomaterials, and therapeutic bioactives has facilitated the development of IHGs for diverse tissue targets, including bone, cartilage, skin, and ocular systems. Looking ahead, future research should focus on the convergence of smart materials, advanced fabrication technologies, artificial intelligence, and bioelectronic interfaces. For instance, next-generation hydrogel coatings could incorporate stimuli-responsive components capable of responding to physiological cues—such as pH, temperature, or inflammation—by releasing antimicrobial agents or dynamically altering their structure. Moreover, hydrogel coatings can be customized to meet the specific functional requirements of different implant types. Orthopedic implants, for example, may benefit from mechanically robust, osteoinductive hydrogels with antimicrobial properties to support bone regeneration and infection control. Conversely, dental implants require coatings that enhance osseointegration while preventing bacterial colonization in the challenging oral environment.

Emerging technologies such as 3D and 4D printing also offer powerful tools for fabricating the next generation of hydrogel coatings for medical implants. By leveraging these techniques, hydrogel layers can be deposited with high spatial precision, enabling the creation of complex, patient-specific geometries and multi-material structures. 4D printing introduces time as a design variable, allowing hydrogels to change shape or function in response to physiological stimuli such as temperature, moisture, or pH. This dynamic adaptability can enhance the performance of hydrogel-coated implants by promoting better tissue integration, controlled drug release, and real-time responsiveness to the biological environment. As these printing technologies continue to evolve, they hold great potential to revolutionize the customization and functionality of hydrogel coatings.

Future research should navigate the integration of AI-driven methodologies, including machine learning and computational modelling, to advance the design and application of implantable hydrogels. These approaches offer robust platforms for the rapid analysis of large datasets, enabling the prediction and optimization of hydrogel properties in relation to physiological behavior, therapeutic bioactivity, and controlled drug release. In parallel, next-generation hydrogel technologies should explore the role hydrogels as reliable biomedical interfaces in the development of implantable bioelectronic devices for diagnostics, therapeutics, and tissue regeneration. Owing to their hydrophilicity, ECM-mimicking properties, and excellent biocompatibility, hydrogels can serve as effective mediators between electrochemical devices and biological tissues. This interface can facilitate the development of bioelectronic systems characterized by enhanced biocompatibility, reduced immune response, mechanical compliance, and efficient conductivity.

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